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Deliverable 3.1

Initial design of real-time control and VNF intelligence mechanisms

Abstract

This document presents the current status of the WP3 activities. It contains the discussion on both cross-WP activities, such as the analysis of the control loops and the challenges related to the inclusion of NI at a very fast timescale, and the details on the specific algorithms related to the different WP tasks. Overall, D3.1 contains information about 11 innovative algorithms and solutions that deal with the fast timescale application of NI in mobile networks. The project KPIs, targeted by this work package, are mainly related to the energy efficiency and the reliability of the system.

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Table of Contents

1	Introduction.....	13
2	Functional architecture	14
3	Control loops and network exposure.....	16
3.1	Robustness and optimality control	16
3.2	Requirements from the algorithms.....	17
4	Compute-aware radio scheduling.....	19
4.1	Reliable distributed unit for virtualization	19
4.1.1	The problem.....	19
4.1.2	Background	21
4.1.3	Diagnosis.....	23
4.2	Cloud acceleration for virtualized RANs.....	24
4.2.1	LDPC 5G decoding measurements.....	24
4.2.2	System design.....	25
4.2.3	Computing resources scheduling and radio allocation algorithms.....	25
4.3	Application-aware radio scheduling	25
4.4	Compute-aware scheduling for analytics VNF	28
4.4.1	Motivation	28
4.4.2	System model and problem formulation.....	29
4.4.3	Proposed solution and evaluation.....	29
4.4.4	Summary.....	30
5	Multi-timescale edge resource management	31
5.1	AI-enhanced edge orchestration	31
5.1.1	Introduction and motivation.....	31
5.1.2	Architecture of AI-enhanced management and orchestration system	33
5.1.3	Summary.....	34
5.2	WLAN performance prediction for spectrum management.....	34
5.2.1	Introduction.....	35
5.2.2	Background	36
5.2.3	The problem formulation	37
5.2.4	A GNN model for performance prediction in next-generation WLANs	38
5.2.5	Results.....	39
5.2.6	Conclusion	42
5.3	Energy aware edge resource management	42
5.3.1	The problems	42
5.3.2	Understanding energy consumption	43
5.3.3	Combining VNFs at the edge.....	46
5.4	Data-driven resource orchestration	48
5.4.1	Motivation	48
5.4.2	Dataset description.....	49
5.4.3	Device Population Profiles.....	51
5.4.4	Resource Management Approach.	52
5.5	Multi-timescale network slice reservation.....	54
5.5.1	Motivation	54
5.5.2	System model and problem formulation.....	54
5.5.3	Proposed solution and evaluation.....	55
5.5.4	Summary.....	55
6	Reconfigurable intelligent surfaces control	56
6.1	Motivation	56
6.2	Notation.....	56

6.3	System model.....	57
6.4	Problem formulation.....	58
7	In-backhaul learning.....	59
7.1	Introduction and motivation.....	59
7.2	PISA architecture.....	59
7.3	Methodology.....	60
8	Conclusion and outlook.....	61
9	Appendix A: State of the art.....	62
9.1	Compute aware network functions.....	62
9.2	Edge-aware resource orchestration.....	62
9.2.1	Edge to cloud orchestration.....	62
9.2.2	MANO solutions.....	63
9.2.3	Resource management techniques for fog/edge computing.....	64
9.2.4	Edge computing for video analytic services.....	64
9.2.5	Radio resource management in wireless networks.....	65
9.2.6	Challenges in edge orchestration.....	67
9.3	Reconfigurable intelligent surfaces.....	68
9.4	Energy aware operation.....	68
9.4.1	Energy-aware code offloading.....	68
10	References.....	70

List of Figures

Figure 1. The algorithms studied by WP3 and reported in this deliverable.	14
Figure 2. The workflows in WP3.	15
Figure 3. The overall architecture described in D2.1.	16
Figure 4. The different approaches analyzed by WP3.	16
Figure 5. MAPE-K for Machine Learning functions.	18
Figure 6. Virtualized RAN architecture.	19
Figure 7. Every TTI ($=1$ ms), a worker must execute a DU job, comprised of a pipeline of interdependent DU tasks to process UL SF n and DL SF $n + M$, within $M - 1$ ms.	19
Figure 8. Two vDUs competing for resources. The UL/DL data load of vDU 1 is the highest possible while vDU 2's is variable.	20
Figure 9. Decoding time of one transport block in a dedicated CPU core using Intel FlexRAN.	20
Figure 10. Computing fluctuations and head-of-line blocking of DU tasks may cause that a worker violates its job's deadline, incurring loss of connectivity, as shown in Figure 8.	20
Figure 11. Subframes and PHY radio channels (FDD), $M = 4$	21
Figure 12. LTE and NR DU pipeline: DU n	22
Figure 13. Throughput performance for both uplink and downlink (top). CPU time required by different PHY layer functions (bottom). Different uplink/downlink load (relative to the maximum) and channel conditions (SNR).	23
Figure 14. Decoding time and associated power consumption when using LDPC FEC to decode transport blocks with different MCS and different SNR.	24
Figure 15. Centralized and joint control of radio and computing resources in an heterogeneous cloud of accelerating processors.	25
Figure 16. Functional blocks in application-aware radio scheduler.	26
Figure 17. P4-PRAN emulation platform for application-aware radio scheduler.	27
Figure 18. Typical data and video traces.	27
Figure 19. Visualization of the statistics of the collected data. (a) shows the "confidence" metric against the decision variables, (b) shows the "frame-rate" (latency) metric.	28
Figure 20. Visualization of the statistics of the collected data (c) and (d) show the frequency of each metric value for two different configurations.	29
Figure 21. The flow of execution of a decision step. the encoding, window, and NN input are decision variables. The frame rate and accuracy are performance metrics.	29
Figure 22. (Left) Average regret of the proposed method. (Right) Cumulative confidence & frame rate.	30
Figure 23. Reward (cumulative confidence) in different number of users, APs, and GPUs.	30
Figure 24. The architecture of multi-domain AI-enhanced management and orchestration system for V2X use cases.	32
Figure 25. Average response time and CPU utilization of vCDN server deployed in our PoC.	34
Figure 26. Usage of ML predictors for network optimization.	36
Figure 27. 5 GHz band and its channel configurations.	36
Figure 28. Channel selection applying DCB.	37
Figure 29. Example of a WLAN deployment. On the left, the topological view of the deployment. On the right, the graph representation of the deployment.	38
Figure 30. GNN model architecture.	39
Figure 31. Architecture of the state-of-the-art models.	39
Figure 32. Mean and standard deviation of the obtained RMSE by all models on the test data set.	41
Figure 33. SAVRUS approach overview highlighting meaningful components.	43
Figure 34. MNO monitoring approach.	50
Figure 35. Comparison among devices: connected cars, other IoT verticals, and smartphones.	52
Figure 36. Car Brands Comparison; figures show diurnal per car values, log scaled, and normalized.	52
Figure 37. Request scheduling for optimal resource allocation at real time.	53
Figure 38. Adaptive Scheduling of Edge Tasks (ASET) workflow.	53
Figure 39. Percentage of successful queries over time for ML task with users arriving in real-world pattern.	53
Figure 40. Network slicing markets. SPs reserve resources from operators' equipment with the aim of maximizing efficiency in their services.	54
Figure 41. A step in the online decision making framework.	55
Figure 42. Regret and violation convergence with Budget $B=10$, and slots (i.e., smaller time scale) = 5.	55
Figure 43. Regret and violations convergence in different mixed-scale setups.	55
Figure 44. Radio massive access scenario overcoming NLOS issues by means of RISs installed on the building glasses. It might support different use cases, such as AR-glasses, e-health, video-surveillance, Industrial-IoT.	57
Figure 45. The Ingress stage of the PISA architecture.	59

Figure 46. Logical mapping between match and action elements of the PISA architecture (on the left) and levels of a Decision Tree (on the right).60

List of Tables

Table 1. KPI Targeted by WP3 and the candidate technology	15
Table 2. MAPE-K for the application aware radio scheduling (see Sec 4.3)	17
Table 3. MAPE-K for the WLAN channel bonding (see Sec 2.2)	18
Table 4. LTE and NR Channels	22
Table 5. Classification performance.....	28
Table 6. Features used per experiment.	40
Table 7. Details of the quality measured numerical variability models (NVM) used to validate SAVRUS	45
Table 8. Algorithms' execution time	48

List of Acronyms

2G – Second Generation
3G – Third Generation
4G – Fourth Generation
5G – Fifth Generation
6G – Sixth Generation
AF –Application Function
ADAM – ADaptive Moment estimation
AI – Artificial Intelligence
API – Application Programming Interface
AR – Augmented reality
B5G – Beyond 5th Generation
BBU – Baseband Unit
BS –Base Station
CNF – Cloud-native Network Function
CNN – Convolutional Neural Network
CPS – Cyber Physical System
CPU – Central Processing Unit
COTS – Commercial Off The Shelf
CU – Central Unit
CQI – Channel Quality Indicator
CRAN – Cloud Radio Access Network
DL – DownLink
DNN – Deep Neural Network
DNS – Domain Name Service
DQN – Deep Q-Network
DRA – Diameter Routing Agent
DRL – Deep Reinforcement Learning
DU – Distributed Unit
eNB – evolved Node B
ES – Exponential Smoothing
ETSI - European Telecommunications Standards Institute
FCNN – Fully Connected Neural Network
FIFO – First In, First Out
FL – Federated Learning
GMM – Gaussian Mixture Model
gNB – next generation Node B
GPU – Graphical Processing Unit
GTP – General Packet Radio Service (GPRS) Tunneling Protocol
HDD – Hard Disk Drive
IMSI – International Mobile Subscriber Identity
IP – Internet Protocol
IPX – Internet Protocol eXchange
IMEI – International Mobile Equipment Identity
IoT – Internet of Things
IoU – Intersection over Union
KL – Kullback–Leibler

KPI – Key Performance Indicator
LA – Learning Agent
LFU – Least Frequently Used
LRU – Least Recently Used
LSTM – Long Short-Term Memory
LTE – Long Term Evolution
M2M – Machine To Machine
MANO – MANagement and Orchestration
mAP – mean Average Precision
MAP – Mobile Application Part
MAPE – Monitor, Analyze, Plan and Execute
MBS – Macro Base Station
MCF – Multi-Commodity Flow
MCS – Modulation and Coding Scheme
MDP – Markovian Decision Process
MEC – Multi-access Edge Computing
MILP – Mixed Integer Linear Programming
MNO – Mobile Network Operator
MSE – Mean Square Error
MVA – Mobile Video Analytics
MDP – Markov Decision Process
ML – Machine Learning
MLP – MultiLayer Perceptron
MOS – Mean Opinion Score
NF – Network Function
NFV – Network Function Virtualization
NFVI – Network Function Virtualization Infrastructure
NI – Network Intelligence
NN – Neural Network
NRT – Near Real Time
NS – Network Service
NSSI – Network Slice Subnet Instance
NWDAF – NetWork Data Analytics Function
OCO – Online Convex Optimization
OPEX – OPerating EXpenses
OS – Operating System
OSM – Open Source MANO
OSFPF – Optimal Service Function Placement Framework
OTAF – Optimal Task Assignment Framework
PDP – Packet Data Protocol
PNF – Physical Network Function
PoE – Power-over-Ethernet
POMDP – Partially Observable Markov Decision Process
PRB – Physical Resource Blocks
PUSCH – Physical Uplink Shared Channel
PUCCH – Physical Uplink Control Channel
QoS – Quality of Service

QoE – Quality of Experience
RAM – Random Access Memory
RAN – Radio Access Network
RAPL – Running Average Power Limit
RCS – Rich Communication Services
REC – Reduction of Energy Consumption
ReLU – Rectified Linear Unit
RNN – Recurrent Neural Network
RF – Radio Frequency
RIC – RAN Intelligence Controller
RL – Reinforcement Learning
ROS – Robot Operating System
RT – Real Time
RTT – Round Trip Time
RU – Radio Unit
SAE – Stacked AutoEncoder
SBS – Small Base Station
SCCP – Signaling Connection Control Part
SDN – Software Defined Networking
SDR – Software Defined Radio
SF – Small Factor
SFC – Service Function Chain
SIM – Subscriber identity Module
SIP – Session Initiation Protocol
SLA – Service Level Agreement
SLO – Service Level Objective
SMO – Service Management and Orchestration
SMT – Satisfiability Modulo Theories
SNR – Signal to Noise Ratio
SS7 – Signaling System 7
STP – Signaling Transfer Point
TAC – Type Allocation Code
TES – Thresholded Exponential Smoothing
TIS – Tasks Implementation Selector
TPC – Transmission Power Control
TTL – Time-To-Live
UCI – Uplink Control Information
UE – User Equipment
UL – UpLink
URLLC – Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communications
VAE – Variational Autoencoder
vBS – virtualized Base Station
VIM – Virtual Infrastructure Manager
VM – Virtual Machine
VMNO – Virtual Mobile Network Operator
VN – Virtual Network
VNF – Virtual Network Function

VNFM – Virtual Network Function Manager

VoIP – Voice over IP

VR – Virtual Reality

vRAN – virtualized Radio Access Network

WLAN – Wireless Local Area Network

Executive summary

This deliverable presents DAEMON's initial view on the problem of real-time control and network functions intelligence. The work presented in this document tackles two main points:

- Understanding what the main challenges from the architectural perspective are and proposing initial solutions to overcome them. This activity has a strong relationship with the work carried out in WP2 in terms of requirements and architectural design. Namely, we identified additional requirements that are specifically related to the fast timescale NI applications.
- The design of specific NI algorithms that focus on the inclusion of NI very close to the user plane. A lot of attention was paid to edge network functions, such as those related to the access network (including Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces).

In total, we describe 11 algorithms. These algorithms can be generally categorized into two main classes:

- Algorithms that jointly optimize radio and compute resources for intelligent NFV in vRANs. These algorithms are mainly presented in section 4 and deploy novel mechanisms and techniques for solving such difficult and coupled decision-making problems.
- Algorithms that are capable of running on different timescales. These algorithms are of specific interest to the work package as they directly tackle the highly heterogeneous nature of edge and fog domains and are mainly presented in section 5.

Each proposed algorithm specifically mentions the targeted KPI so as to create a clear, propaedeutic environment for the follow-up WP5 activities.

Sections 6 and 7 set up important initial problem formulations on the topics of intelligent reconfigurable surfaces and in-backhaul learning, respectively. Specifically, the metrics of a RIS-aided networking performance are derived in section 6, while in section 7, a critical examination of current approaches for in-backhaul learning is presented to pave the way for contributions in this regard.

1 Introduction

The application of network intelligence solutions for solving network-related problems has been rocketing in the past few years. In DAEMON, we propose a critical view on this aspect, striving for a truly network intelligent native architecture that can impact the future generations of mobile networks. As this is a compound and very complex problem, in WP3, we focused on the fast timescale applications of Network Intelligence, namely the ones that deal with edge resources and network functions that are very close to the user plane.

In this environment, the application of NI is particularly challenging for a number of reasons:

- The fast pace of NI decisions: due to the closeness to the data plane, decisions shall be taken within very few milliseconds from the triggering events. This imposes constraints on the complexity.
- The limited availability of data: the context that could be gathered at the very edge of the network could not capture other contextual data coming from, e.g., other edge deployments or the overall status of the network.

In WP3, we thus developed algorithms that deal with these aspects and aim to improve the network under very specific KPIs such as the reliability of the system, its pure performance and, most importantly, its sustainability, reducing the energy consumption of the system.

The first two sections in this document present the overall framework of the work package to provide context for the algorithms introduced in the following sections. The main structure of this deliverable can be summarized as follow:

- Section 2 describes the overall framework of the WP3 system, describing how the different algorithms presented in this document interplay to build the overall WP vision.
- Section 3 details some architectural considerations about the introduction of NI at the edge, namely how to guarantee robustness and optimality given the conditions and the possible control loops for fast timescale NI.
- Section 4 analyses the activities related to the WP task of compute aware radio scheduling. Namely, contributions related to virtualization, cloud acceleration, and generalized optimization models for scheduling different VNFs are presented and evaluated.
- Section 5 studies the WP task of multi-time scale edge resource management. Intelligent data-driven solution for edge orchestration and resource management are presented, discussed, and initially evaluated.
- Section 6 considers reconfigurable Intelligent surfaces and sets up the targeted requirements in this domain in terms of a well-defined problem formulation whose solution is being currently investigated.
- Section 7 focuses on backhaul learning and critically surveys current early works in this field with an aim to identify the bottlenecks in fast time scales NI solutions.
- Section 8 concludes the deliverable with a brief summary, main insights, and expected future work.

Additionally, this deliverable contains a state-of-the-art section where the most recent works related to each proposed algorithm are summarized and critically reviewed. For better readability, the state-of-the-art is condensed in Appendix A.

2 Functional architecture

The ecosystem envisioned by DAEMON and initially drafted in D2.1 is composed by a number of components that bring the Network Intelligence (NI) natively into the mobile network architecture. By following the initial guidelines for the architecture drafted in D2.1, we devised an ecosystem of solution that are building to the overall goal of the WP. In particular, the work carried out by this work package is related to the inclusion of NI very close to the data plane, directly in network functions and controllers. That is, WP3 studies all the interactions between NI directly embedded in the VNF software, or conveniently located in controllers such as SDN controllers, gNB DU controllers, or edge orchestrators. According to the domain scope, we could depict them as in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. The algorithms studied by WP3 and reported in this deliverable.

The algorithms proposed by WP3 address very diverse area of the mobile network, ranging from the very far edge up to the backhaul, following the data path from mobile terminals. More specifically:

- Edge and Far edge user plane functions: access networks are one of the two traditional building blocks of mobile network, together with the core. In the context of softwareized network architectures this boundary has become blurred up to the point that software-based solutions can provide a continuum between domains. However, the quest for unperceivable latencies and very high bandwidth, fostered the research in the area of edge computing. In this document, we will explore solutions for both pure access network technologies such as novel pipelines for the encoding and decoding of wireless frames and the operation of reconfigurable surfaces.
- Resource provisioning and management at the edge. In order to provide the resources needed by the different applications that are studied in this document, precise and fast management and orchestration solutions need to be devoted. More specifically, we consider a broad range of wireless network problems, dissecting them from the management and orchestration perspective.
- Learning in the backhaul. The last mile of the edge to core continuum is represented by the backhaul connectivity. In this document we will also discuss how the different switches and forwarding elements in the network can be leveraged to learn from the traffic.

All these solutions can be arranged to form a compound ecosystem, that includes theoretical modelling of the data needed for network intelligence to the prototyping of system where the NI is finally enforced. This is depicted in Figure 2 below. In this Figure we depict all the interactions between the NI algorithms designed by WP3, and how their interconnection i) builds towards the WP objectives and ii) introduce new requirements in the network architecture.

Figure 2. The workflows in WP3.

In a nutshell, WP3 activities can be summarized into three main categories:

- Novel data modelling for the creation of NI, leveraging input data coming from the edge. This will be of particular importance for the attaining of the sustainability related KPIs, which require a deep understanding of the energy consumption profile of network functions.
- Novel network functions prototypes, which can embed NI solutions in an efficient way. Such network functions can represent a step forward
- Precise orchestration solution to manage such functions at the edge, that can leverage on the modelling discussed above.

All these solutions contribute to achieving the WP objectives, especially in terms of performance KPIs.

Table 1. KPI Targeted by WP3 and the candidate technology

KPI	Target Value	Candidate Technology	Section
VNF Energy Savings	50%	Reliable distributed unit for virtualization, Cloud Acceleration for virtualized RANs, Compute Aware scheduling analytics	4.1, 4.2, 4.3
Computing resource savings	40%	Reliable distributed unit for virtualization, Cloud Acceleration for virtualized RANs, Compute Aware scheduling analytics, AI-enhanced edge orchestration, Data-driven resource orchestration	4.1, 4.2, 4.3, 5.1, 5.4
Response time of AI-based NI algorithms	1-ms	In-backhaul learning	7
OPEX Savings	60%	Data-driven resource orchestration, Multi-timescale network slice reservation	5.4, 5.5
Wireless Capacity Increase	100%	Reconfigurable intelligent Surfaces Control, WLAN traffic classification and performance prediction	5.2, 6

As summarized in the above table, the KPIs targeted by the solutions devised in the Work Package, besides the common goals of maintaining the network performance in terms of throughput and latency high, focuses on three main areas:

- **Overall cost reduction:** many of the solutions proposed in this work package are targeting the improved efficiency in terms of resource utilization which, in turn, will have benefits in terms of monetary expenditure as less computing resources need to be deployed, operated and powered.
- **Fast AI reaction times,** especially when the intelligence is located close to the data plane, as in the case of backhaul.
- **Improved wireless efficiency,** both in the edge and beyond edge.

The enhanced NI functionality proposed in the WP requires enhanced control loops and exposure of network data to and from the network. We review these features next.

3 Control loops and network exposure

The aim of DAEMON is to bring NI in all levels of the networks ranging, creating a native way of including it directly into the network architecture. As already discussed in D2.1, the algorithms designed by DAEMON shall follow guidelines on interactions with the network, as depicted in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3. The overall architecture described in D2.1.

Due to the characteristics of the algorithms developed in WP3, some of the guidelines are especially relevant for the decision-making model employed by the algorithms. For instance, the real-time deadline imposed by many of the WP3 algorithms are limiting the availability and the richness of the data. As the control timescale dimension is reduced due to the characteristics of the problems studied in this work package, particular attention shall be paid to Robustness and Optimality of the solutions.

3.1 Robustness and optimality control

NI models are trained with data gathered from the network, and possibly keep learning online, during the network operation, through reinforcement learning techniques. However, due to the very fast reaction times, model training and updates at the network edge cannot be performed at wire speed, for a number of reasons, including the possibly long training times and the lack of availability of specialized hardware such as GPUs.

Thus, the environment shall include modules and interfaces that allow the NI Orchestration, as discussed in D2.1, to continuously monitor and possibly update the NI modules running at the edge. So far, we identified two possible strategies for this task, as depicted in the Figure 4 below.

Figure 4. The different approaches analyzed by WP3.

The first one, depicted on the left part of Figure 4, envisions a loop between the NI Orchestration (i.e., the element that manages the NI in the network, deployed at different domains) and the VNFs. The interaction has two directions:

- From NI Orchestration to the Network Function: the NI Orchestration picks the best NI model and algorithms to perform specific tasks, such as the ones described in this document (e.g., the application aware radio-scheduling algorithm described in Section 4.3)
- From the Network Function to the NI Orchestration, reporting on the achieved KPI (which are usually optimized by the NI) and some information about the context (i.e., the network conditions observed at the moment). This information allows the NI Orchestration to monitor the KPIs and understand whether the context associated to the NI is still the one originally used for the training

However, this approach could be limiting for some use case, which may require a tighter interaction between the "drift" control and its actual implementation. Thus, in a second approach (depicted in right left-hand side of Figure 4) the NI orchestrator is onboarding an additional diagnostic module that can perform such computations on the drift very close to the network functions, trying to maximize the performance of the system at any point in time.

3.2 Requirements from the algorithms

In order to fully integrate the algorithms into the overall architecture, it is fundamental to understand what are the needed interfaces that algorithms use to interact with their environment. For this purpose, we adopted a methodology already used by the MAPE-K (Monitor-Analyze-Plan-Execute over a shared Knowledge) feedback loop, one of the most influential reference control model for autonomic and self-adaptive systems [1].

In a nutshell, the MAPE-k specifies how the different modules have to interact with the system, as follows:

- The Sensors specify all the probes that are needed to gather the input data and the kind of input data we have to gather. In principle, the APIs are specified at this level.
- The analyze block includes any pre-processing, summary, or preparation of the data such as averages, auto-encoders, clustering algorithms.
- The Plan includes the specific NI algorithm that is implemented, for instance a Neural Network fulfilling a categorization task.
- The Execute part specifies how the algorithm is going to interact with the system and possibly change configuration parameters.
- Finally, the Effector include the specific configuration parameters we are updated in the Network Function, again specifying the API.

We performed this exercise for a number of algorithms available in the following subsections, we report here some of them.

Table 2. MAPE-K for the application aware radio scheduling (see Sec 4.3)

Block	Description
Sensor + Analyze	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Amount of (transport or buffer) resources used by each bearer (carrying video or data traffic) - Indication of the congestion level of the air interface
Plan (policy)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - determine the optimal system configuration that can handle the future evolution of the (video and data traffic) demand, e.g., <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o how the scheduler should be set to provide the right priorities to some kinds of traffic (e.g., video) - Often implemented via a classifier, based on a) determined clusters in a feature space, b) K nearest neighbor algorithm or c) neural network
Knowledge (assessment of the current policy)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A loss function that indicates which penalty to pay for the system misidentifying (e.g., video as data or data as video) the provided examples in the training (or validation) set
Execute + Effector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Applications will utilize the corresponding APIs to the resource domain-specific controller to realize the scheduler decision.

Table 3. MAPE-K for the WLAN channel bonding (see Sec 2.2)

Block	Description
Sensor + Analyze	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - State of the links (Signal-to-Interference-plus Noise (SINR) ratio, Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) from users' links= - Allowed channel configurations by Access Points (APs) - Optional: distance among users and APs. - Optional: Users' traffic demands
Plan (policy)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A controller triggers the system's performance evaluation. - A reconfiguration of the bonded channels might be triggered if the performance is low. - A RL algorithm is used to take the decision
Knowledge (assessment of the current policy)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitored data - Current setup - Best performance predictor - Possible channel configurations - Learned channel configuration selection policy
Execute + Effector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The controller changes the configuration of the managed APs. - SDN could be used for that purpose.

Both the algorithms specify different kinds of input data, two different ways of training a neural network (supervised learning and reinforcement learning) and a re-configuration trigger for the network function. By summarizing the algorithms in this way, we will be able to devise the kind of interfaces that will be needed for the DAEMON Native NI Architecture. Still, we performed changes to the original MAPE-K framework to take into account the specificities of the network solutions.

Figure 5. MAPE-K for Machine Learning functions.

More specifically, two modules shall be added to the plain MAPE-k depending on whether the NI algorithm is based on supervised or reinforcement learning. For the former, as depicted in Figure 5, the knowledge module shall be integrated with a learning functions that specifies a training definition that includes aspects such as the input data shape, batches, and most importantly, the used loss function (which could be dynamically adjusted, indicated as objective functions). The learning box is instead playing the role of the State / Action representation and the reward table when we consider reinforcement learning functions. Additionally, the effector and the sensors can be also redirected to a digital twin, if it is needed, to either sandbox the decisions before actually implementing them in a real system or have a reference elements to study possible deviations of the learning algorithms.

Through the adaptation of the different algorithms with the k-MAPE, we will provide inputs towards the definition of the architecture in WP2.

4 Compute-aware radio scheduling

The convergence between the radio and computing domains is paving the way to promising new technologies that can reduce costs, increase flexibility, and robustness of mobile networks. In the next sections we explore four new promising topics in this area:

- The design of reliable gNB functions (Section 4.1);
- The design of computing clouds to accelerate radio processing operations (Section 4.2);
- Application-aware allocation of radio resources (Section 4.3); and
- Offloading of computing tasks to radio-enabled edge computing infrastructure (Section 4.4).

These four areas cover a wide set of promising technologies that are investigated in DAEMON.

4.1 Reliable distributed unit for virtualization

The virtualization of radio access networks (RANs), based hitherto on monolithic appliances over ASICs, will become the spearhead of next-generation mobile systems beyond 5G. Initiatives such as the carrier-led O-RAN alliance [2] have spurred the market and the research community to find novel solutions that import the flexibility and cost-efficiency of network function virtualization (NFV) into the very far edge of mobile networks.

Figure 6. Virtualized RAN architecture

Figure 6 shows the architecture of a vRAN, with base stations (BSs) split into a central unit (CU), hosting the highest layers of the stack; a distributed unit (DU), hosting the physical layer (PHY); and a radio unit (RU), hosting basic radio functions such as amplification or sampling. As depicted by the figure, vRANs shall rely on cloud platforms comprised of pools of shared computing resources (mostly CPUs, but also hardware accelerators brokered by an abstraction layer), to host virtualized functions such as the PHY.

However, while CUs are amenable to virtualization in regional clouds, virtualized DUs (vDUs)—namely, the vPHY therein—require fast and predictable computation in edge clouds. Shared computing platforms provide a harsh environment for DUs because they trade off the predictability supplied by dedicated platforms for higher flexibility and cost-efficiency. Indeed, research has shown that resource contention in infrastructure, even when placing virtual functions on separate cores, may lead to up to 40% of performance degradation compared to dedicated platforms—the so-called *noisy neighbor problem*.

This is certainly an issue for traditional network functions such as virtual switches, firewalls, or even CUs, where metrics such as tail latency are particularly relevant. Consequently, substantial effort has been devoted to the design of generic scheduling frameworks that can balance computing efficiency and latency performance [2]. However, as we show next, the requirements associated with full-fledged DUs are harder: violating deadlines cause users to lose synchronization with the DU, which leads to connectivity collapse.

4.1.1 The problem

To ease the explanation, we focus on frequency division duplex where uplink (UL) and downlink (DL) transmissions occur concurrently in different frequency bands, and on 5G's baseline numerology ($\mu = 0$ in 3GPP TS 38.211) with one transmission time interval (TTI) per subframe (SF) and SF duration of 1 ms.

Figure 7. Every TTI (=1 ms), a worker must execute a DU job, comprised of a pipeline of interdependent DU tasks to process UL SF n and DL SF $n + M$, within $M - 1$ ms.

Figure 7 illustrates the basic operation of the baseline 4G/5G DU processor. Every TTI n , a worker initiates a DU job comprised of a pipeline of tasks (hereafter referred to as DU tasks): (1) process data and (2) control channels carried by UL SF n , (3) schedule UL/DL radio grants to be transported by DL SF $n + M$, and (4) process data and (5) control channels for DL SF $n + M$. A worker executes a DU job in a thread, using computing resources allocated by a task scheduler; and multiple workers perform DU jobs in parallel to handle one DL SF and one UL SF every TTI. Importantly, given 3GPP specification (see details in Section 4.1.3), there is a hard constraint on M that imposes a computing time budget of roughly $M - 1$ ms to process each DU job (usually, $M = 4$).

Violating this constraint has critical consequences on DUs. To illustrate this, we set up an experiment with two DUs implemented with vanilla srsRAN ($M = 4$), each one associated with one user implemented with srsUE and virtualized over Linux containers sharing 5 Intel Xeon x86 cores @ 1.9GHz. In this experiment, vDU 1 transmits and receives as much data as possible. Conversely, vDU 2 transmits and receives traffic following a random process with different parameters, which

generate normally-distributed computing workload with the mean (line) and variance (shaded area) shown at the bottom of Figure 8: the higher the load variance of vDU 2, the larger the fluctuations of the computing capacity available for vDU 1.

Figure 8 (top) depicts vDU 1's relative network throughput in yellow ("Baseline") as a function of the workload produced by vDU 2. The figure shows that the performance of vDU 1 quickly deteriorates. The reason is that, because both vDUs share the same CPU pool, vDU 1 occasionally suffers from CPU resource deficit when vDU 2 produces a peak in demand. As a result, vDU 1 workers executing DU jobs violate their deadline to send out the corresponding DL SF, as illustrated in Figure 10, which causes the user to lose synchronization and throughput to drop.

Figure 8. Two vDUs competing for resources. The UL/DL data load of vDU 1 is the highest possible while vDU 2's is variable.

Figure 9. Decoding time of one transport block in a dedicated CPU core using Intel FlexRAN.

Figure 10. Computing fluctuations and head-of-line blocking of DU tasks may cause that a worker violates its job's deadline, incurring loss of connectivity, as shown in Figure 8.

Indeed, completing a DU job every TTI is vital to preserve synchronization between the BS and its users and thus attain reliability. However, this is challenged by some compute-intensive operations within DU tasks such as forward error correction (FEC). These operations require substantial processing time even when using solutions such as Intel FlexRAN [3] or Agora [4], which exploit data parallelization, efficient work scheduling, or SIMD programming. More specifically, FlexRAN provides open libraries to perform FEC, rate matching, and cyclic redundancy checks. In turn, Agora builds on FlexRAN to process UL and DL data in data channels (part of DU tasks 1 and 4) with a solution that is optimized for multi-core CPU platforms. A more in-depth revision of related literature can be found in Section 9.1. To illustrate this, Figure 9 shows the time required by FlexRAN to successfully decode 4-Kbyte transport blocks modulated with 64QAM, encoded with LDPC and 1/3 code rate, and for different signal-to-noise-ratio (SNR) regimes between 10 dB and 30 dB, in a dedicated CPU core. Note that, albeit these approaches provide high-performing solutions, they require dedicated computing platforms with deterministic performance to perform reliably.

Generic computing (or task) schedulers allocate computing resources to DU workers depending on the platform's capacity and the scheduler's policy. However, different DU tasks (pipeline stages) in the pipeline shown in Figure 7 (in one DU job) cannot run in parallel in different computing cores to expedite the latency of a job because of the inter-dependencies between DU tasks, which cause head-of-line blocking. For instance, UL channels (DU task 1) have to be processed before scheduling UL/DL data (DU

task 3), or data grants (DU task 3) must be computed before processing DL data (DU tasks 4) and control channels (DU task 5). More details in Section 4.1.3. The obvious solutions applied today in the market, namely, *dedicated* hardware acceleration and over-dimensioning, diminish the very reasons that make virtualization appealing for the RAN in the first place: flexibility and cost-efficiency. On the one hand, research has shown that shared platforms require 5x more resources than dedicated platforms to attain similar performance guarantees in real mobile networks. On the other hand, dedicated accelerators make vDUs more expensive and power-hungry than their pure HW counterparts—let alone the fact that the much-longed hardware/software decoupling is not achieved.

In summary, optimized schedulers and baseband libraries are obviously important but these solutions cannot provide hard latency guarantees for every DU job and, as a consequence, *do not provide carrier-grade reliability in non-deterministic platforms*. Hence, we must find new solutions to enable reliable vRANs without compromising the advantages of virtualization.

4.1.2 Background

In this section, we first introduce the fundamentals of 4G LTE and 5G New Radio (NR) that are relevant to understand this work (Section 4.1.2.1). Then, we present the details of the baseline PHY pipeline architecture introduced earlier (Section 0).

4.1.2.1 A primer in LTE and NR PHY

Figure 11. Subframes and PHY radio channels (FDD), $M = 4$.

NR adopts orthogonal frequency division multiplexing access (OFDMA) with cyclic prefix (CP) for both DL and UL transmissions, which enables fine-grained scheduling over a time-spectrum grid, and multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) techniques. While LTE also adopts OFDM in the DL, it relies on single-carrier FDMA (SC-FDMA) for the UL, a linearly precoded flavor of OFDMA that reduces peak-to-average power ratio in mobile terminals.

An example of the radio operation for FDD is depicted in Figure 11. In the time domain, each frame is comprised of 10 subframes (SF), each with 1-ms duration. Each SF comprises 2 slots, each with 7 (with normal CP) or 6 (with extended CP) OFDM symbols for LTE; and one or more slots, each with 14 (with normal CP) or 12 (with extended CP) OFDM symbols for NR, depending of the (flexible) OFDM numerology employed, which is configurable in 5G. Accordingly, a transmission time interval (TTI), which specifies the time resolution for scheduling, is equal to 1 ms in LTE and configurable to one or multiple slots in NR. Without loss in generality, we will assume a TTI is equal to 1 ms (baseline numerology in NR) to simplify our explanations. In the spectrum domain, SFs comprise a number of subcarriers with inter-subcarrier spacing equal to 15 kHz in LTE and variable, between 15 kHz and 240 kHz, for NR. LTE and NR support different bandwidth configurations up to 20 MHz and 100 MHz, respectively. The time-spectrum grid is divided into channels that are summarized below. A physical resource block (PRB), comprised of 12 subcarriers and 1 slot, is the smallest radio resource unit that can be allocated; and a transport block (TB) carries data using a variable number of PRBs. The size of a TB depends on the state of higher-layer (MAC, RLC) data buffers and the selected modulation and coding scheme (MCS), which in turn depends on the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). Every TTI, PDSCH (for DL) and/or PUSCH (for UL) carry one TB (or two, in some MIMO settings) per user. The allocation of radio resources is indicated by DL and UL grants, which are encoded into PDCCH's Downlink Control Information (DCI) as shown in Figure 11. Hybrid automatic repeat request (HARQ), combining forward error correction (FEC) and ARQ, is used for error control. To this end, explicit feedback is received from the users in UL Control Information (UCI) carried by PUSCH or PUCCH, as shown by the dotted arrows in the figure, and TBs are encoded with low-density parity-check codes (NR) or turbo codes (LTE).

More details can be found in [5] and references therein.

Table 4. LTE and NR Channels

Downlink Channels and Signals	
PDSCH	Physical DL Shared Channel: Carries user data, higher-layer user information and paging, as indicated in PDCCH.
PDCCH	Physical DL Control Channel: Carries resource assignments and UL scheduling grants.
PBCH	Physical Broadcast Channel: Carries basic information about the BS, e.g., bandwidth.
PHICH	(LTE only) Physical HARQ Indicator Channel: Carries UL Hybrid-ARQ feedback.
PCFICH	(LTE only) Physical Control Format Indicator Channel: Indicates the format used for PDCCH and PHICH.
PSS/SSS	Primary/Secondary Synchronization Signals: Signals used for synchronization and BS identity.
Uplink Channels and Signals	
PUSCH	Physical UL Shared Channel: Carries user data as indicated in PDCCH and, optionally, UL Control Information (UCI).
PUCCH	Physical UL Control Channel: Carries UCI including feedback (HARQ, channel quality, etc.) and scheduling requests.

4.1.2.2 Baseline DU pipeline

The above operations are inter-dependent, e.g., PDCCH in DL SF n carries the grants needed to process PDSCH in DL SF n and PUSCH in UL SF $n + M$, UCI in UL SF n carries feedback required to compute DL grants in DL SF $n + M$, HARQ feedback from PUSCH processing in UL SF n is required to compute grants in DL SF $n + M$, etc. All of them are required by a DU. To do this, every TTI n an idle worker performs a DU job n comprising the pipeline of Figure 12:

- Process uplink subframe n (received during TTI n):**
 - First, wireless samples corresponding to the n^{th} UL SF are transformed into OFDM symbols by performing Fast Fourier Transformation (FFT) and CP removal.¹
 - Then, the PUSCH and PUCCH are demodulated, decoded and processed, providing UL TBs and UL feedback (DL HARQ, channel quality, scheduling requests).
- Compute UL/DL grants carried by DL SF $n + M$:** Schedule DL and UL radio resources considering UL feedback.
- Process downlink subframe $n + M$:**
 - First, base signals are processed, including PSS/SSS, PBCH, and, in case of LTE, PCFICH.
 - Then, the PDSCH and the PDCCH are processed, encoded, and modulated, according to the UL/DL grants.
 - Finally, the encoded OFDM symbols corresponding the DL SF $n + M$ are converted into wireless samples by adding CP and performing inverse FFT (IFFT). The corresponding wireless samples are then sent to the radio transmission chain, with sub-ms transportation delay δ , at time $n + M$.¹

Existing DU solutions implement the above baseline pipeline using highly-optimized libraries such as Agora or FlexRAN to expedite some operations involved therein via parallelization, SIMD programming, or dedicated hardware accelerators.

Figure 12. LTE and NR DU pipeline: DU n .

¹ This task may be offloaded to the RU in O-RAN.

4.1.3 Diagnosis

The design presented in Section 0 is not suited for non-deterministic computing platforms such as shared clouds. Namely, existing solutions implementing the above baseline pipeline cannot guarantee the timely execution of individual jobs without the assistance of *dedicated* hardware acceleration or aggressive over-dimensioning, which compromise flexibility and cost-efficiency.

Timing constraints. 3GPP defines several timing constraints. Relevant to our work are K_3 (latency between ACK/NACK reception in UL UCI and the corresponding DL re-transmission in PDSCH), and K_4 (latency between PUSCH reception and delivery of HARQ feedback). In LTE, $K_4 = 3$ ms, which implies $M = 4$. Though these timings are more flexible in NR, they are set at longer timescales by the CU, and $M = 4$ is the usual choice. As a consequence, there is a hard deadline to process each DU job within $M - 28 - 1$ ms, as shown at the bottom of Figure 12. Violating this deadline prevents timely delivery of DL SFs and, as a result, loss of synchronization and connectivity between the DU and its users, as shown by the baseline performance in the experiment of Figure 8.

Inter-task dependencies. Regardless of individual processing optimizations, different DU tasks within a job have strong dependencies as shown by the blue arrows in Figure 12:

- DL grants must be computed before PDSCH because they carry information required to encode and modulate DL TBs;
- PUSCH and PUCCH must be processed before computing DL grants because these channels carry users' feedback (DL HARQ, channel quality, etc.) in UCI messages (dotted arrows in Figure 11), which is required to schedule DL data appropriately;
- UL HARQ feedback can only be computed after processing PUSCH; and this feedback is required to schedule UL grants within the same job to satisfy 3GPP timing constraints;
- UL grants must be computed before processing PDCCH, which carries those grants, and (in case of LTE) before processing PHICH, which carries UL HARQ feedback.
- All the channels and other basic signals (PSS, SSS) must be processed before generating time-domain signals (IFFT).

As a result, known implementations (e.g., srsRAN² and OpenAirInterface³) perform each DU job in a single-thread pipeline (Figure 12), or in a multi-thread pipeline where each thread has to wait and be executed in a precise order, which boils down to Figure 12 again. Although solutions like Agora and FlexRAN help to accelerate the processing of individual DU tasks, the aforementioned dependencies prevent running different DU tasks in a job in parallel to expedite the pipeline of Figure 12.

Figure 13. Throughput performance for both uplink and downlink (top). CPU time required by different PHY layer functions (bottom). Different uplink/downlink load (relative to the maximum) and channel conditions (SNR).

Non-deterministic tasks. As hinted in our toy experiment shown in Figure 8, the computing time required by DU tasks highly depends on the instantaneous availability of computing resources. We note moreover that the most compute-intensive tasks also depend on the context, that is, on the data load (rate of TBs to decode/encode) and on the mobility patterns of the users (signal quality) [6], which can induce very quick fluctuations in the demand for computing resources. To illustrate this, we deploy the baseline vDU, implemented in srsRAN [7], processing downlink and uplink traffic over one Intel i7 core in a 10-MHz band. Figure 13 depicts the achieved throughput in both the uplink and downlink (top subplots), and the median time incurred by the CPU to perform DU tasks (bottom subplots). We take these measurements for different load intensities (relative to the capacity in UL and DL, respectively) and average signal-to-noise ratios (SNR) indicating the channel quality for both UL and DL, and adapt the MCS to minimize the

² <http://www.srsran.com/>

³ <https://www.openairinterface.org/>

workload issued by the decoder (differently to our results in Figure 9). The results yield two observations. First, processing PDSCH and (especially) PUSCH are the two tasks that consume CPU time the most, which is not surprising as it has been observed before [6]. Second, while the CPU time of the rest of tasks (and others not shown in the figure to reduce clutter) remains practically constant,⁴ the time required to process PDSCH and PUSCH highly depends on the context; that is, on the SNR—and so on the mobility patterns of the users, and on the load—and hence on the users behavior. Note that even if shared pools of hardware accelerators are used *à la cloud* to reduce the processing time of some of these tasks, queueing in the abstraction layer brokering access to the accelerators across multiple vDUs incur in similar issues.

Conclusion: Because of the above, baseline solutions cannot guarantee the timely completion of DU jobs when facing computing fluctuations, which cause unreliability in scenarios such as that of Figure 8]. We hence claim that a re-design of the DU pipeline is required to attain high reliability (K5 of DAEMON KPIs; see Objective 4 of GA) of vRAN solutions in non-deterministic computing platforms such as shared clouds.

4.2 Cloud acceleration for virtualized RANs

With the Virtualization of Radio Access Network (vRAN) being one of the most challenging tasks in the context of the application of NFV paradigm into 5G networks, it is important to provide an efficient resource control framework for both radio and computing resources involved in the processing of vRAN functionalities. In particular, we focus on 5G LDPC decoding, i.e., one of the most resource-consuming components of the uplink radio communication processing pipeline. We consider this problem in an innovative setting that involves heterogeneous sets of computing resources to serve network tasks, with both GPU and CPU implementations of LDPC decoding that can be leveraged. This makes the problem especially complex, owing to the strong non-linear coupling between radio and computing policies ruling vRAN operation, and to the diverse performance-energy consumption trade-off of CPUs and GPUs. In this context, deep learning models are a suitable tool to develop a resource control framework able to jointly take radio and computing allocation decisions.

4.2.1 LDPC 5G decoding measurements

In order to get performance measurements of LDPC 5G decoders, two different implementations have been analysed over a Linux platform: (i) the CPU-based library flexRAN from Intel running on an Intel Xeon Gold 6240R CPU and (ii) the GPU-based library cuPHY from NVIDIA running on a NVIDIA A100 GPU. Measurements collected reflect different user conditions in a mobile network environment, expressed in terms of Signal-to-Noise-Ratio (SNR), Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS), and Physical-Resource-Block allocation (PRB). The following figures show performance in terms of decoding time and power consumption for the two implementations, when the maximum allocation of 250 PRBs is given to the user. Results show that the GPU implementation yields much lower decoding times due to its ability to process in parallel the many coded blocks coming from the Transport Block to be decoded for all the user contexts observed, but on the other hand this comes with a pretty much higher power consumption.

Figure 14. Decoding time and associated power consumption when using LDPC FEC to decode transport blocks with different MCS and different SNR.

⁴ To be precise, the processing time of these tasks does vary with the number of users (e.g., scheduling becomes more complex). However, our results indicate this is negligible compared to that of data processing tasks.

4.2.2 System design

The vRAN system analysed in this work is composed of N base stations whose task is to serve the decoding requests coming from users within a deadline due to the time constraints of the baseband uplink processing pipeline. Assuming that the uplink frames of all base stations are synchronized in time, at the beginning of each timeslot, an agent observes the current context and automatically performs radio allocation for the requests (in terms of PRB, or equivalent bits) and schedules them to either a CPU or a GPU according to a customizable scheduling policy. The goal of the agent is to take optimal radio and scheduling decisions so that the overall throughput of the system is maximized, which means maximizing the number of radio-scheduled bits that is successfully decoded in time out of the users' uplink transmission buffers and reducing the unnecessarily scheduled radio resources. In such an optimization problem, also energy consumption due to GPU and CPU utilization can be considered, either as a penalizing term for the overall throughput or as a hard constraint of the system. The following figure schematizes the system.

Figure 15. Centralized and joint control of radio and computing resources in a heterogeneous cloud of accelerating processors.

4.2.3 Computing resources scheduling and radio allocation algorithms

To perform radio allocation decisions and assign decoding requests with computing resources, two possible classes of algorithms can be utilized: in the first one, the two tasks are treated separately and in the second one the algorithm takes jointly radio and resource assignment decisions. Regarding the first algorithm, (i) radio allocation is performed by a reinforcement learning model that is reading the context (expressed as characteristics of decoding requests coming from users in terms of SNR and bits) and performing an action in terms of radio allocation (bits); (ii) computing resource assignment is instead performed by a model which is estimating the expected decoding time of the requests and assign them one by one to the resource guaranteeing the earliest deadline. Concerning the second class of algorithms, instead, both radio allocation and computing resource assignment are jointly performed by a reinforcement learning model that is reading the context (expressed as characteristics of decoding requests coming from users in terms of SNR and bits and the current queue occupancy of the computing resources) and performing actions in terms of radio allocation (bits) and computing resource assignment. In both cases, according to the system design described in the previous paragraph, the reinforcement learning models can only compute the reward for a given action (performed at $t - \tau$) only after 2τ microseconds at time $t + \tau$.

Through the usage of accelerated vRAN processors, a better overall resource utilization can be achieved, to support a sustainable usage of the infrastructure.

4.3 Application-aware radio scheduling

In 5G and beyond generations, the RAN domain is expected to provide new advanced digital services than traditional communication services, such as high-definition video streaming (see 2nd row of Table 1). A key goal of mobile operators is to properly allocate limited (radio and network) resources to different traffic flows to meet the real-time needs of applications. In this sense, 3GPP defined several new 5G QoS Identifiers (5QI) to characterize different QoS flow requests (for example, guaranteed bandwidth), and then map the QoS flows into the radio bearer, which is the smallest granularity in the RAN user plane. However, this approach has its limitation in allocating adequate resources for the corresponding quality of experience (QoE) under time-varying conditions. For example, different video quality options of

streaming services, such as 360p, 480p, 720p, have their respective recommended sustained speed (cf. system requirements in [8]), which can be used as a guide for resource allocation. To overcome this limitation, we investigated the application-aware radio scheduling in this section, and the goal is that the RAN can not only be application-aware but also adjust the corresponding scheduling policy.

Moreover, several prior arts are reviewed in the last paragraph of Sec. 9.1 and we can notice that they rely on identifying specific ports (e.g., HTTP uses port 80 and HTTPS uses port 443) or by deep packet inspection. In comparison, we seek for implicit traffic identification based on the traffic characteristics not only to avoid port spoofing and privacy issues⁵ but also to enhance the future extendibility to new applications. In detail, the application-aware radio scheduling architecture in the RAN domain relies on two components as shown in Figure 16:

- 1) The first component is a block that classifies bearers in various predefined classes (e.g., video, bandwidth-greedy data, web browsing, gaming, etc.). This classification is done based on how the traffic arrives over the bearer, possibly in both directions. Typically, the evolution of the RLC (radio link layer) buffer occupancy is used for this purpose.
- 2) The second component is the policy guidance that provides applied policies for underlying scheduler(s), e.g., give priority to certain classes of traffic (e.g., video, gaming) over others (e.g., bandwidth-hungry data), but also make the class that gets priority keep its traffic below a given limited rate. Note that the radio scheduler at the RAN DU can assign resource block(s) to corresponding radio bearers and the transport network (TN) scheduler can shape the traffic based on the information from the policy guidance.

Figure 16. Functional blocks in application-aware radio scheduler.

To realize these two functional blocks of application-aware radio scheduler using real-world application and user plane data, we implement the P4-PRAN emulation platform in the following which is composed of CN, disaggregated RAN entities, P4-based software switch, several VM-based UE instances, and a UE management dashboard (see Figure 17). More details of the platform will be provided in WP5 deliverables.

To design the classifier, we consider the following initial use case. There are two classes: data and video. The former corresponds to applications that always have data to send and want to send it as quickly as possible. The latter corresponds to adaptive video, where the video client downloads chunks of a video stream and the quality in which the chunks are downloaded is determined by the video client based on how fast it sees the information coming in. The aim is to give priority to adaptive video streaming over data (e.g., large file in FTP server) downloads, so that it can just download the video in the highest quality.

The classifier relies on a supervised machine learning technique: it is trained off-line based on labelled data and then deployed. To collect labelled (training, validation, and test) data the following experiments were performed. On a subset of UEs large file (i.e., data) downloads were started, while on the other subset of UEs an adaptive video application was initiated. The RLC buffers associated to each of these UEs were sampled every 10ms and the retrieved samples were reported every sec, so that there are 100 RLC buffer samples collected per sec.

Figure 18 shows 25 randomly selected traces of the RLC buffer occupancy evolution of typical data and video flows over 20sec. Based on this trace the classifier needs to determine whether the trace belongs to the video or data class. The experiments run provide labelled data to be used to train, validate and test the classifier. Remark that the 20 sec RLC buffer evolution can be seen as a 2000-dimensional vector x_n with $n = 1, \dots, N$ and N the number of samples in the data set. With each such vector a label c_n is associated which determines to which class the vector (i.e., trace) belongs to. This labelled data set is

⁵ Deep packet inspection is not allowed to take place in Europe if communications data are used by companies to target advertising or by governments to block politically sensitive content.

split into a training set (part of which is sometimes considered to be a validation set) and a test set. The training set contains 75% of the data, the test set the rest.

Figure 17. P4-PRAN emulation platform for application-aware radio scheduler.

Figure 18. Typical data and video traces.

For classification various algorithms are considered: a simple threshold-based solution as benchmark, a K nearest neighbors algorithm and a feed forward neural network classifier.

Threshold-based algorithm: This simple algorithm is inspired by Figure 18: if the average buffer occupancy (measured over 20 sec) is below a threshold, it is classified as video, otherwise as data. The optimal threshold was determined by choosing that value that makes the correct classification as much as possible on the training set.

K nearest neighbors algorithm: When a new vector x_{new} is presented to this algorithm, it determines the K closest neighbors in the training set, then it determines the labels that are associated to these neighbors and takes a weighted majority vote to determine the class associated to this new vector. In the results below, we choose Euclidean distance as distance metric, $K = 4$ and the weights are the inverse of the distance.

Feed forward neural network: We chose a neural network with an input layer of 2000 neurons and an output layer of 2 neurons (each one identifying a class). We considered 4 hidden layers with 40 neurons each. The activation function for all neurons, except the output layer, is ReLU, where $ReLU(x) = x$ if $x > 0$ and 0 otherwise. The output layer has softmax as its activation function. As loss function we used categorical cross entropy and as training we used ADAM. During training 20% of the training set was used as validation set. We trained as long as needed for the loss function to stabilize on the validation set.

Ultimately the classification performance should be expressed as how much the QoE (quality of Experience) of the end users increases, but that evaluation we reserve as future work. As an alternative we evaluate the performance, by assessing the misclassification of each of these algorithms on the test set. The results are given in Table 5.

Table 5. Classification performance.

Algorithm	Data classified as video	Video classified as data
Threshold-based	4.8%	8%
K nearest neighbors	2.7%	4.8%
Neural network	2.6%	8.4%

4.4 Compute-aware scheduling for analytics VNF

Along the work package's efforts of leveraging the convergence of compute and radio towards more efficient networking, we present here a compute aware scheduling for video analytics. The state-of-the-art in computer-aware scheduling for the tackled application is detailed in section 9.2.4.

4.4.1 Motivation

The problem of offloading tasks from mobile devices to the edge has gained immense interest in the networking community, and it is one that is still actively researched. The importance and popularity of this problem stem from the fact that considerable Quality of Experience improvements is possible if the scheduling decisions (i.e., offloading parameters) are optimized efficiently. The difficulty, however, is that such optimization should consider both: The characteristics of the radio used to communicate with the edge and the characteristics of the computing tasks to be offloaded itself (i.e., the communicated information). In this sub-section, we introduce our contribution on edge analytics scheduling in Wi-Fi environments [9]. Specifically, we consider the object recognition in video frames as our analytics task, where a mobile device capturing a video aims to recognize the object in those videos with the maximum accuracy possible and minimum latency with the help of an edge server. An additional burden to solve this problem is that it is intrinsically online, i.e., we do not know the results of our offloading parameters (to be described later) until after we actually execute them. Thus, the device needs to optimize these decisions based only on past information and without future knowledge of the communication medium status (channel state) or the task status (the content of the image). This is the exact problem we are aiming to model and address here.

- Experimental motivation through real data [10] (Dataset available): To show the effect of multiple decision variables on the scheduling process, we built a testbed consisting of an Android phone that captures images through the mobile's camera, performs JPEG encoding, and transmits the compressed images to an edge server through a wireless 802.11ac Access Point. The collected data documents "latency" and "cumulative confidence" measurements that were obtained from this experiment. The records are obtained for different values of "image encoding rate" (i.e., compression) and "Neural Network input layer size" decisions. The delay is also provided with details on different phases: transmitting the frame wirelessly, decoding and rotating at the server, and performing object recognition with YOLO on the server's GPU. Moreover, we document the achievable frame rate as a result of the total latency. An analysis of the data (Figure 19) shows the effect of the chosen decoding and neural network size on the performance metrics we chose. Although these effects seem consistent in (a), (b), this is mainly due to taking the average across all images. Figures (c), (d) demonstrates the variability in these metrics across the same configurations, motivating the necessity of tuning these parameters at run-time.

Figure 19. Visualization of the statistics of the collected data. (a) shows the "confidence" metric against the decision variables, (b) shows the "frame-rate" (latency) metric.

Figure 20. Visualization of the statistics of the collected data (c) and (d) show the frequency of each metric value for two different configurations.

4.4.2 System model and problem formulation

In the sequel we define the main components of our system model. We specify the decision variables that we optimize as well as our utility function.

- Decision variables: at each reconfiguration period t , we set the compression ratio for each device n (i.e., encoding) $x_{n,t}$, the window size (i.e., time slice of the reconfiguration period dedicated for processing n 's data) $w_{n,t}$, and the neural-network input size variable y_t (i.e., the down-sampling).
- Objective function: we aim to match the best policy in hindsight. That is, a policy with full knowledge regarding the future (next time slot) accuracy and frame rates. Specifically, we aim to find a sequence of decision variables $\{z_t\}_t$ such that $\sum_{t=1}^T E[f_t(z^*)] - E[f_t(z_t)]$ goes to 0 asymptotically, while respecting the latency constraints $E[g_{n,t}(z_t)] \leq 0$ as well as the time slicing constraints $\sum_{n \in N} w_n \leq \Delta$ where the variable z_t groups all decision variables, and Δ is the reconfiguration period.
 - Specifically, the objective function is defined as the sum of obtained cumulative confidences across all users, given a random frame observation $o_{nt} : f_t(z_t) = \sum_{n \in N} C_{nt}(z_t; o_{nt})$. As for the frame rate constraint, given a random channel state h_{nt} , it is set as $g_{nt}(z_t) = \lambda_n - R_{nt}(z_t; h_{nt})$, where λ_n is the target frame rate for user n , and R_{nt} is a random function that characterizes the obtained framerate.

Figure 21 shows the details of a decision step. (i.e., decision variables execution and then objective/constrained functions reveal).

Figure 21. The flow of execution of a decision step. the encoding, window, and NN input are decision variables. The frame rate and accuracy are performance metrics

4.4.3 Proposed solution and evaluation

This sub-section presents the proposed algorithm for solving the formulated problem as well as the evaluation method.

- Solution algorithm: Herein we provide an overview of the developed algorithms. Due to the online nature of the problem, it is natural to consider multi-arm bandits formulation in which the actions (arms) are the encoding and NN size decisions, and the rewards are the cumulative confidence. We extend this typical bandit formulation in two ways: exploiting the correlation between similar actions, and respecting the latency/frame rate constraints.
 - For exploiting the unknown correlation between actions, we use a Gaussian Process (GP), which utilizes a kernel function $\rho(z, z')$ to express the objective/constraints function value of any pair. This leads to the known GP-UCB algorithm, which has not been applied to constrained cases, such as ours.
 - As for the constraints, we preceded the usual GP-UCB steps (i.e., action) calculation by first going through an expansion phase in which we successively create and enlarge the

action set through adding actions that are guaranteed to respect the constraints (i.e., by means of upper bounds).

- Finally, after reaching a satisfactory set of actions (i.e., a set whose size is close to that of the maximum achievable safe set), we start the conventional GP-UCB algorithm, which essentially consists of posterior update on the unknown objective/constraints values, confidence interval formulation, and then picking the decision variable with the highest upper bound on the confidence interval. The regret of this procedure is guaranteed to asymptotically reach 0 [9].
- Simulation setup and experimental results: we consider the compression set of $X = \{25, 50, 75, 100\}$ and an NN input size set of $Y = \{128, 192, \dots, 576\}$. As for the time window portions, we set $W = \{0.1, \dots, 0.9\}$. (The decision variable $z \in X \times Y \times W$). The system is reconfigure each (i.e., an online decision is made) $\Delta = 5$ seconds.
 - First, we consider 2 users with minimum frame-rate requirements of $\lambda = 10$ and 20, and we plot the average the average regret with time in Figure 22.a, which confirms that the policy (i.e., online decisions) are zero-regret. In Figure 22.b, we see the performance in terms of cumulative confidence and frame rate simultaneously (on different axis). Initially, the images are over-compressed, leading to a smaller data size and lower latency. Thus, we observe the high frame-rate but an unsatisfactory performance in terms of cumulative confidence. However, as time progress the policy is more balanced and does achieve high confidence while respecting the required frame-rates.

Figure 22. (Left) Average regret of the proposed method. (Right) Cumulative confidence & frame rate.

To demonstrate the generality of the proposed solution framework, we additionally evaluate the framework for three different settings: (i) Multiple GPUs (i.e., each user can configure the neural network size differently), (ii) the number of users N is higher than the number of GPUs, and (iii) the users can be served J Access points. Specifically we set $N = 4; K = 2; J = 1$ for Scenario (ii), and $N = 4; K = 2; J = 2$ for Scenario (iii). It can be seen that the reward (sum of confidences) keeps improving towards the optimal one. The observed performance is within 6%, 4% and 5% of the optimal in each Scenario, after 200 slots.

Figure 23. Reward (cumulative confidence) in different number of users, APs, and GPUs

4.4.4 Summary

We have showed, through practical experiment and a detailed analysis of the resulting dataset, that compute-aware scheduling algorithms of video analytic tasks are necessary due to volatile and data-dependent performance. We then designed such a compute-aware online framework and ensured that it makes no assumption on the form of the objective and constrained function. The approach firstly identifies feasible networking and learning parameters and then deduces online actions that provably reach those of the best in hindsight. The results briefly presented here, and detailed in the paper [9], contributes to the KPI2 of compute resource savings since users are using optimal NN sizes and hence not consuming extra compute resources to unnecessarily run larger models.

5 Multi-timescale edge resource management

As 5G services impose stringent requirements to network management and control, such as unperceivable latency and pseudo-infinite bandwidth, in the DAEMON we bring NI within VNFs deployed in the Edge/Fog domains to perform data analysis and decision-making at timescales of milliseconds or lower (NI at Real-Time Controllers). However, the Edge/Fog domains are usually characterized by a set of scarce, strongly heterogeneous, and highly distributed resources, which is significantly challenging for traditional policy-based edge resource management and orchestration solutions. Thus, the resource control problems that occur at the Edge/Fog need to be carefully studied and addressed by DAEMON's NI algorithms that will make decisions in a swift manner. In this section, we present the work that has been carried out towards studying the challenges of real-time control and VNF intelligence as a part of multi-timescale edge resource management, such as i) adapting NI to constrained environments (energy-constrained computing infrastructure, shared spectrum) (Section 5.3), ii) coordinating decentralized and functionally decoupled orchestration and control engines that operate at different timescales (Edge/Fog vs. Cloud) (Sections 5.1, 5.2, and 5.4), and iii) learning zero-touch self-learned NI across a set of geographically distributed controllers and orchestrators (across multiple Edge/Fog domains and Cloud) (Sections 5.1 and 5.4).

5.1 AI-enhanced edge orchestration

In this section we describe our efforts to create a Management and Orchestration (MANO) system for training and testing NI algorithms tailored for multi-timescale edge orchestration. Such a system will serve as a baseline for creating proof-of-concepts that will be used for evaluating the impact of AI/ML on the edge orchestration decision-making processes. The NI algorithms for optimal VNF scaling, placement and migration of different timescales (milliseconds or less in WP3, and larger than milliseconds in WP4), will be placed and evaluated in such an environment at the Edge/Fog level, leveraging an interplay between Edge and Cloud. The description of the AI-enhanced MANO system that we provide in this section specifically addresses challenges of a particular 5G and 5G vertical, i.e., Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) systems, with no restrictions on applying the same management and orchestration techniques on the services belonging to other 5G verticals.

5.1.1 Introduction and motivation

The potential of integrating AI/ML techniques to NFV MANO systems is well recognized in the research circles (as presented in Section 9.2), and there are some important research efforts invested to study this topic [11] [12] [13] [14], with the specific focus on enforcing NFV MANO operations and automating them. Reactive approaches for service continuity that requires a set of NFV MANO operations (i.e., proactive service placement, scaling and/or migration), only adjusts a configuration after an event happened (e.g., vehicle moves to a location that can be served by a closer or more suitable edge node) [15]. Such approaches are getting replaced or complemented by proactive ones, which leverage data analytics, and AI/ML, for the anticipation of such event and the in advance preparation of the network [15]. However, there is still a gap in research when it comes to experimentation and testing the true impact of AI/ML on the optimization of NFV MANO operations. To this end, we present the AI-enhanced MANO system for V2X services in with cloud and edge orchestration layers, which are enabled to autonomously operate, but also to collaborate and balance their operations towards achieving desired Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). Such an AI-based MANO system is suitable for inspecting the true impact of AI/ML on the edge orchestration operations, thereby helping to identify the gaps in the current deployments, and to deploy and test the fast decision-making NI algorithms.

Some of the reasons why edge orchestration operations of 5G and beyond services need to be automated are given as follows:

- a demand for new use cases for industry 5.0, Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), and self-driving vehicles, which require extensive broadband, efficient, resilient, and reliable connectivity, and network availability of five-nines [12];
- improving operational efficiency in NFV systems, as network complexity significantly increases with heterogeneous and distributed resources and services [14];
- dynamic changes in KPIs happen due to fluctuations in demands from verticals (e.g., IIoT, vehicular systems), user mobility patterns, etc., thus, network needs to improve its operation by learning from the environment and optimizing itself towards the desired and promised KPIs [12];
- complexity and heterogeneity, brought by combining different technologies and verticals in 5G and beyond, require NFV MANO systems that enable an intelligent interplay between edge and cloud [12];
- NFV MANO operations (e.g., service placement, migration, fault recovery, scaling) need to be further optimized and automated in 5G ecosystems with the help from AI/ML, as traditional

optimization techniques are complex and lengthy, and heuristics are near-optimal, which might make them both ineffective in swift response to dynamic changes in the network [14]; and

- management and orchestration of computational resources in 5G and beyond becomes a major challenge, due to the practices of cloudification and virtualization of core network functions, and partially radio access network functions [11].

The integration of AI/ML into NFV MANO systems for 5G and beyond is expected to mitigate most of the challenges listed above, as it is now mature enough to provide efficient solutions for complex optimization and prediction problems [11]. If used in a suitable manner (e.g., very fine-grained AI algorithms carefully chosen for operation in a specific network domain), AI/ML can enable i) optimized service instantiation, ii) learning utilization patterns for computational resources of virtualized network services, iii) prediction models for proactive resource allocation/relocation, and iv) optimized service migration. Besides the aforementioned benefits, AI/ML techniques impose some additional challenges that need to be taken into account. Some of them are vulnerabilities in terms of i) security, scalability, and transferability [14], which limit the full potential of applying AI/ML to NFV MANO in 5G, ii) high computation power that might not be available in resource constrained edge nodes, and iii) need for quality data to train the ML algorithms, as their performance on making decisions (e.g., predicting, classification, taking actions) will depend on how close was the training data to the actual data used in production environments.

Figure 24. The architecture of multi-domain AI-enhanced management and orchestration system for V2X use cases.

The AI-enhanced MANO system for V2X services that we present in this section, and illustrate in Figure 24, consists of two layers, i.e., Cloud and Edge. The system enables autonomous MANO operations in each of the domains, but enforces an interplay between them for offloading orchestration decisions, or for retrieving data from distributed data engineering pipelines available in all edge domains. Such a system orchestrates both services and applications developed for various use cases, but also Network Intelligent Functions (NIFs) that are represented by adopted and integrated AI/ML models. Despite the emerging popularity of bringing intelligence to network management and orchestration functions in 5G and beyond, most of the works on validating the impact of AI/ML on MANO are based on simulations. There is a gap between using synthetic data and real data when it comes to training and validating/testing AI/ML models, as real setups can create more realistic traces for training, with higher probability of good performance when deployed in production environments. However, building realistic Proof-of-Concepts (PoCs) is usually time-consuming and expensive, while the number of scenarios that can be covered is limited. On the other hand, simulators bring that flexibility but mostly at the cost of not capturing all dynamics of real environments. Thus, the real setups are fundamental to create hybrid approaches that ensure that the performance of AI/ML algorithms is not negatively impacted once they are dealing with real data. One of the attempts to pursue testing of AI/ML on the lifecycle management operation of scaling service functions is presented by Baranda et al. [13], where a scaling operation of virtual Content Delivery Network (vCDN) service is triggered by AI/ML algorithms, thereby integrating AI/ML into management platform of 5G-Transformer project. Thus, in Section 5.1.2, we present and illustrate the architecture of AI-enhanced MANO systems, which can be used as a baseline for creating realistic experimentation environment that extends the scope of aforementioned PoC. This MANO system enables studying and experimenting with AI-enhanced operations of proactive placement, scaling, migration, and termination, of challenging V2X services, towards understanding and resolving challenges imposed by AI/ML to overcome them and improve those MANO operations.

5.1.2 Architecture of AI-enhanced management and orchestration system

The architecture of multi-domain MANO system presented in Figure 24. is applicable to all distributed and heterogeneous softwarized networks whose operation stretches from edge to the cloud, where services and applications are usually deployed with microservice-based approach, and connectivity ensured via different wireless technologies including 5G and beyond. As such networks are usually characterized by distributed resources belonging to different edge domains, which might belong to different Mobile Network Operators (MNOs), we follow the split between cloud (i.e., centralized) and edge orchestrators, which are deployed in a relationship $m : n$, $m < n$, $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$.

Thus, each edge domain that consists of one or multiple edge nodes (i.e., MEC hosts) is governed by one edge orchestrator, which is, following ETSI NFV MANO framework, in charge of lifecycle management (e.g., instantiation, scaling, termination) of all underlying services, i.e., i) use case-related services, ii) value-added services, and iii) NIFs that embody AI/ML models. These edge orchestrators also enable cross-edge collaboration, as well as learning zero-touch self-learned NI. On the other hand, cloud orchestrator is rather in charge of global optimization in the system, thereby making less-granular decisions depending on the e.g., locations and density of vehicles on the roads for our particular real-life use case. One particular example of these decisions is service migration from one edge domain to another, triggered by higher density of vehicles (i.e., edge service consumers) in one edge domain, or by need for optimization of energy consumption in MEC hosts across edge domains (one example of NI algorithms that will be developed in WP4). Two MANO layers communicate with each other in the two following ways: i) via Edge-Cloud reference point, which is used to either offload decision-making tasks between two orchestrators or to pass the already taken decision, and ii) via message brokers, which exchange data in a controlled way depending on the type of AI/ML technique that has been applied in the system, thereby using that data to either perform training or model adjustments and online learning. Thus, depending on the time-scales of optimization (global or local, i.e., edge-specific), it is required that MEC hosts can connect data to AI/ML models in a transparent and efficient way. In case of federated learning, which is suitable for distributing intelligence across edge nodes, thus deploying AI/ML agents in edge nodes, we consider that each edge orchestrator trains the local model based on the data collected from its own domain. On the other hand, if security in data sharing between two message brokers laying in two orchestration layers can be preserved, multi-agent reinforcement learning may use data collected from other edge domains to optimize policies.

Some examples of V2X services that might benefit from such AI-enhanced NFV MANO system are:

- *infotainment services*, such as vCDN, where cloud orchestrator optimizes distributed vCDN deployment across edge domains, based on the locations of vehicle (e.g., retrieved from the location service) and computational resource utilization in each of the edges (e.g., collected from message brokers in edges) [16] [17];
- *emergency services*, such as lane clearance for emergency vehicles, where edge orchestrators optimize service operation on the edge level, while cloud orchestrator makes sure that service is deployed in all edge domains that are on the route affected by emergency situation [18];
- *maneuver recommendation services*, which provide vehicles with recommendations about which lane to drive in, when to merge or exit the lane, etc., taking into account location, speed and destination of vehicles (e.g., retrieved from cloud orchestrator) [19].

Having hierarchical MANO system for the services listed above is important because of the orchestration load distribution. As presented in an experimental evaluation of collaborative orchestration among edges [18], the increase in number of requests for orchestration operations (e.g., numerous services that serve an increased number of vehicles need to be scaled up/out, or migrated from one edge to another) significantly impacts the response time of an edge/cloud orchestrator per orchestration request. If a vehicle that is moving with the speed of 80km/h, thereby receiving maneuver recommendations or instructions to support emergency situation on the road, is waiting for an edge service to be scaled for more than 500ms (duration of scaling operation), it will result in at least 500ms delay in a road information update delay. Such a delayed notification, caused by delayed and reactive scaling operation from the edge orchestrators, will prevent vehicle to e.g., change the lane in a timely manner, as it will already pass the additional 11.1m on the road [18]. Thus, if the decision for scaling is taken earlier by an edge orchestrator, given the input from AI/ML models that predict the resource consumption and density of vehicles, the scaling operation will not affect the service operation.

Each edge and cloud orchestrator can act as a subscriber for various types of data that can be stored on edges, and used for training or online learning/optimization. If we consider vehicle as a client, the client application running in the vehicle communicates with the edge services via long range 4G/5G and beyond, and it exchanges Cooperative Intelligent Transport System (C-ITS) messages with services, and inform them about its location, speed, heading, and destination. Cloud orchestrator is capable of i) processing decision-offloading requests coming from the edge orchestrators, ii) location data processing and making this data available for all edge orchestrators, iii) injecting decisions on the north-bound interface of edge orchestrators to instruct them to proactively migrate/relocate services from one edge

to another, and iv) receiving notifications from NIFs deployed on the cloud, which enhance their operations and help them make efficient decisions on managing underlying resources and edge orchestrators.

In Figure 25 we show the result of average response time, and CPU utilization, in the case when the vCDN server is deployed on the MEC host, utilizing our Smart Highway and Virtual Wall testbeds as described in [17]. To stress the load and increase the number of vehicles, we run the stress test inside the vehicle, and we can see that the number of vehicles that are simultaneously requesting content from the same server affects the response time, and CPU utilization as well. In case NIF predicts the traffic demand, and the number of vehicles in this specific geographic region, they are expected to optimize edge orchestrator's operation as it will perform horizontal scaling and additional deployments of vCDN server on other MEC hosts, so that users (vehicles) can still experience a low response time. As the response time consists of communication latency (uplink and downlink, impacted by network load), and computational latency (affected by CPU load), its increase is mainly affected by an increase in CPU utilization on edge nodes, which needs to be carefully monitored and optimized e.g., by corresponding NI algorithms running as NIFs. As a part of our future work, we are going to leverage such AI-enhanced MANO system to present the impact of various ML models on the operation of orchestration operations, measured at the client side in terms of response time, throughput, and other relevant KPIs.

Figure 25. Average response time and CPU utilization of vCDN server deployed in our PoC.

5.1.3 Summary

To mitigate the challenges in MANO operations imposed by human interventions (i.e., delayed operations, reactive approach) the automation and intelligence become an imperative for orchestrating services and resources, especially the ones with stringent requirements for latency and capacity, such as those in V2X systems. In this section, we presented our ongoing work on studying AI-based edge orchestration systems, which will be used for training, testing, and validating NI algorithms, allowing us to pursue realistic experimentation and validation of the impact that AI/ML have on the edge management and orchestration in distributed and heterogeneous networks such as V2X systems (aligned with our work WP5). The aforementioned validation of impact will be shown in terms of measuring relevant KPIs. Given the scarcity of edge computing resources, which are especially affected in case of deploying and training/running AI/ML models at the edge, it is important to carefully monitor the utilization of resources, and to build intelligent management systems that will enable i) saving of computational resources at the edge, ii) improving reliability of the managed network and services, iii) decreasing vertical service response time from minutes to seconds (or even less in case of V2X services), and iv) achieving optimality gap of network management decisions that are precise enough to assist faster NI.

5.2 WLAN performance prediction for spectrum management

In its current annual internet report [20], Cisco predicts that devices and connections are growing faster (approx. 10x) than the population. Most of these connections will be machine to machine communications (e.g., IoT devices), smartphones and smart devices. Therefore, it is uncertain whether only one technology will be able to serve the massive internet demand. Most likely, future wireless networks will be based on a combination of technologies that share the spectrum in a geographical area, for instance, Wi-Fi can be used to offload part of the non-priority mobile traffic, releasing some resources for higher-priority mobile traffic. In that sense, non-3GPP technologies, such as Wi-Fi, also must undergo a radical architectural shift to cope with the dynamism, higher-speed, and almost unlimited capacity required by next-generation services. One of them is the shift of the paradigm toward programmable networks that can be holistically orchestrated to offer end-to-end services.

To address the multiplicity of demands, each of them with its own set of requirements, future wireless networks should be fully automated to accelerate service delivery while meeting economical goals. However, current Wi-Fi architecture is unable to offer a high degree of automation, and network providers still rely on manual configuration. Network models and optimization algorithms are developed

for that purpose. In this way, network administrators set an intent [21] as input to the optimization algorithm, and through the model, the algorithm finds the network configuration that fulfills the requirements.

In this section, we take a look to one of the most recent standard-compliant technique to enhance spectral utilization in Wi-Fi, named Channel Bonding (CB). For this particular case, traditional Markov models and other mathematical models have been developed to predict the WLAN performance (e.g., expected throughput) in the presence of interference, given a deployment (e.g., topology) and a particular configuration (e.g., set of channels that could be bonded). These models, that might be inaccurate due to its simplified view of the system (to keep tractability), can be replaced by ML. With a trained ML-model, a Wi-Fi controller can accurately evaluate different configurations in a short timescale. Note that ML-enabled spectrum optimization would require less time to perform a prediction when compared to a traditional model (e.g., Markov model).

In this sense, ML-enabled spectrum optimization can contribute with several KPIs proposed by DAEMON. First, more data can be collected in Software Defined Wide Area Networks (SD-WANs), improving the accuracy of the ML-based models. Second, as ML models predict the WLAN performance faster and more accurately than traditional models, the service response time can be effectively reduced (K8). Finally, a Wi-Fi controller can optimize the spectrum usage by using an enhanced view of the network resources and the aid of ML-based performance prediction, improving its management decisions (K5).

5.2.1 Introduction

Nowadays, network-oriented applications are evolving towards more stringent Quality of Service (QoS)/Quality of Experience (QoE) requirements. To cope with such requirements, recent Wi-Fi amendments have defined new strategies that improve the offered bandwidth to users. In this regard, future Wi-Fi generations are proposing a set of features from which Channel Bonding (CB) is highlighted. CB is a technique introduced in 802.11n that enhances the channel capacity by bonding a maximum of two primary channels in each transmission. Newer Wi-Fi versions allow even more primary channels to be bonded to increase bandwidth [22].

Notwithstanding, the novel mechanisms for next-generation Wi-Fi deployments, addressing the demands of highly dense scenarios, adds more stress to the already scarce spectrum, as more devices will fight for medium access. CB in crowded Wi-Fi scenarios might be counterproductive, as end-user Stations (STAs) might overlap. As a result, the STAs may experience a high number of collisions and suffer excessive starvation [23]. This situation can cause drastic performance deterioration and increase the packet error rate. For instance, dynamic configurations of CB (Dynamic Channel Bonding (DCB)), where the number of bonded channels is adaptively changed depending on network conditions, are recommended to increase the throughput on the one hand (when the channel is not congested), and to alleviate the harmful effects of interference on the other hand (when congestion is high) [24]. However, it is not always clear for an Access Point (AP) which configuration to apply in a given situation of DCB. For that, we argue that performance (e.g., throughput) prediction/estimation could help in optimizing wireless networks by assessing the feasibility of potential system changes. Particularly in CB, performance prediction allows Wireless Local Area Networks (WLANs) to select channel configurations that minimize the inter-Basic Service Set (BSS) interference, optimizing the spectrum usage.

To predict its performance, controllers or APs in a WLAN can use network models to assess how positively or negatively a given decision will impact the performance of the WLAN. Typically, Markov models [25] and mathematical models [26] have been used to characterize WLANs. However, given the increasing heterogeneity in network services and functionalities that are developed to accommodate the extreme imposed requirements, traditional mathematical models do not hold. On the one hand, the Markov chain states increase exponentially with the number of considered devices and their configurations. On the other hand, mathematical approaches rely on simplifying assumptions in order to keep tractability. Moreover, new services and technologies alter the traffic patterns, forcing prediction models to be continuously updated. Therefore, new models are needed that adapt to varying network conditions and environments.

Machine Learning (ML) approaches are proposed as a key component of Beyond 5G (B5G) communications. In the case of WLAN performance prediction, ML can help in the design, planning and operation of a B5G WLAN by creating an interference model from data. By learning from data, ML can build a function that abstract complex network behavior in an ultra-dense WLAN where, given a deployment (e.g., topology), a particular configuration (e.g., set of channels that could be bonded) and the current state of the wireless links, the ML module predicts the expected system throughput. In this way, optimization algorithms placed at controllers can have a reasonable network model to interact with.

A closed control-loop is formed between controllers and predictors that jointly obtain (sub-)optimal system parameters that maximize the expected throughput. Firstly, different measurements are constantly collected from the network and delivered to the controller. The measuring time depends on the kind of decision that is being optimized. Then, the evaluation of different configurations will be executed in a timely manner if a triggering condition is met, for example, if the controller perceives that 50% of their managed devices have lower throughput than expected. In this case, the ML module will generate a prediction for every evaluated configuration. Note that controllers and predictors might operate at different timescales. The controller's decisions might be enforced at longer timescales (e.g., seconds to minutes) while the predictions can be obtained in much shorter timescales (e.g., microseconds to milliseconds), enabling a timely optimization of the spectrum usage to decrease interference and improve the user experience.

Figure 26. Usage of ML predictors for network optimization

5.2.2 Background

A BSS consists of M nodes, one AP, and M=1 STAs (users) associated with that AP. To provide connectivity to several users in an area, multiple APs must be deployed, creating multiple BSSs. When 802.11n/ac/ax APs use the lower part of the 5 GHz band (i.e., the U-NII-1 and U-NII-2 bands), there is a total of eight non-overlapping channels of 20 MHz bandwidth as shown in Figure 27 uppermost part. CB is one of the features [27] introduced in the newest amendments of Wi-Fi [22], [28] to cope with the stringent demands from next-generation services by bonding multiple adjacent channels to create a higher bandwidth channel to potentially increase the throughput of a given transmission. The total bandwidth of CB has grown from 40 MHz (802.11n) to 160 MHz (802.11ac/ax) and it is expected to support up to 320 MHz (802.11be, using the 6 GHz band).

Figure 27. 5 GHz band and its channel configurations.

Under the constraint to bond only adjacent channels, the number of available configurations in a small portion of spectrum is 16 (8 × 20 MHz, 4 × 40 MHz, 2 × 80 MHz and 1 × 160 MHz). With the introduction of novel bonding techniques using Orthogonal Frequency Multiple Access (OFDMA), non-contiguous channels can be bonded, increasing the number of available configurations. Then, every AP is assigned with a contiguous subset of channels from F channels of equal bandwidth, according to a transmission policy. Such transmission policies can be static, dynamic, or probabilistic. In Static Channel Bonding (SCB), the same subset of channels is selected in a per-packet basis transmission. Several works have shown that using the same set of bonded channels in each transmission might be counterproductive, as neighboring nodes might interfere and prevent other nodes from transmitting in a channel (or set of

channels) [23]. These works also showed that the system performance could improve if dynamic CB policies can be applied based on current spectrum usage. For instance, in probabilistic CB, a configuration is chosen with a given probability [29]. Under DCB, the node will transmit over the most extensive contiguous set of channels sensed to be idle right before transmission. In that way, a node can adopt several channel configurations, depending on how many channels are free on a per-packet basis. An evaluation of different channel configurations is presented in [30]. Through simulations, the authors found that CB does not represent a significant increase in the overall throughput when considering a high amount of contending nodes. Instead, better performance is achieved when transmitting over single channels.

Figure 28. Channel selection applying DCB.

5.2.3 The problem formulation

In Figure 28, we assume a transmitting STA in which DCB can be applied over channels 1–4, using configuration C4 or C14 from Figure 27. At time t_1 , the STA senses that only channel 3 is available for transmission, using the Carrier-Sense Multiple Access with Collision Avoidance (CSMA/CA) procedure. Similarly, at t_2 , channels 1 and 2 are sensed to be free at the moment of transmission and the two are bonded consequently. Finally, at t_3 , the STA can transmit over the bonded channels 1–4. Note that, if a SCB policy is applied, the STA can transmit only at t_3 , while if a probabilistic policy is used, any combination of channels can be selected in t_2 and t_3 . Hence, if the network conditions allow it, each AP uses the largest subset of available transmission channels allowed by its policy and depending on the wireless environment. The more channels it can bond, the higher the degree of freedom in selecting channel configurations. In this way, the AP tries to increase the overall throughput. Given the high number of BSS deployed in crowded deployments and the combinatorial nature of CB, it is not always trivial to select the right channel configuration.

Consequently, a careful selection of the transmission channels must be done since selecting the widest subset of available channels can be harmful in the overall long-term throughput and fairness among WLANs [29]. Next-generation WLANs will be able to assess the impact of a given configuration before every transmission takes place through performance prediction models. In dense environments, multiple interactions among devices occur in a matter of microseconds. These interactions vary on a per-packet basis, making each transmission unique. Moreover, the wireless channel capacity where that transmission occurs depends on the channel effects, such as noise and interference and the number of bonded channels. Therefore, figures, such as Signal-to-Interference plus Noise Ratio (SINR), RSSI, bandwidth, Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS), and the amount of time a node can transmit, are crucial to model the wireless environment.

Although extremely accurate, throughput prediction using mathematical models [31] that fully capture the aforementioned channel effects are intractable when considering a higher number of connected devices, thus, they assume smaller deployments. Moreover, most of the existing mathematical models are based on assumptions (e.g., uniform traffic distribution and fixed transmission rate) that lower their complexity but, in turn, disregard the actual phenomena taking place in wireless networks. On the contrary, ML approaches [32], [33] can solve complex problems by learning from data, becoming a powerful network optimization tool. However, the proposed ML models do not exploit the information carried in the deployment's topology.

The introduction of ML in networking optimization aspects is undeniable. Next-generation networks even contemplate the upgrade of certain network functions by learning algorithms. Like the International Telecommunication Union (ITU), several standardization bodies have already defined an architecture where such data-driven ML models assist network communications. As an example, the architecture proposed in [34] suggests using sandboxes, where multiple models can be trained with simulated data that closely resemble the underlying networking system. In this way, the robustness of ML models can be improved. Additionally, such frameworks also contemplate the use of an ML marketplace. Thus, an ML model is chosen depending on the capabilities and the contextual information that a WLAN can gather, e.g., node location and used data rate. Then, a simulation environment is prepared according to this information. The selected ML model is trained and evaluated in the sandbox or changed upon unwanted results. Once the evaluation is done, the ML model is deployed to the live networking system where the

optimization takes place. This process implies that ML models are continuously learning about the wireless environment independently of the deployed technologies or services. For instance, to properly select a channel configuration, a throughput prediction model can be trained in a sandbox, using synthetic data from multiple deployments with multiple channel configurations to evaluate the network performance.

5.2.4 A GNN model for performance prediction in next-generation WLANs

In several applications, data can be defined by graphs where the relationships among samples (or nodes) are represented by the edges between them. Networks are a clear example of such graphs; nodes have their own properties or features and relate to other nodes via the links between them. If there is no link between two nodes, we can generally say that those nodes are not related to each other. Despite their success, ML faces challenges when learning from structured data represented as graphs, as the relationships among nodes are not captured or must be represented differently. For example, typical data preprocessing steps include the generation of a fixed-size matrix (e.g., images of a given size, audio samples or sentences of a fixed length), which represents the sample's information and serves as training data.

To summarize, we advocate the use of GNNs in WLAN performance prediction, given the following:

- GNNs have been successfully applied to combinatorial optimization problems [35], and can achieve relational reasoning [36].
- CB is a problem with a combinatorial action space in dense deployments, where the complexity increases exponentially with the size of the deployment and the number of possible channel configurations.
- The relationships between STAs and APs (connectivity, interference, among others) can be captured via a graph representation, i.e., there is one-to-one mapping between the network topology and the graph representation.
- GNNs are also proposed to solve multiple network optimization processes [37], given their ability to generalize to large-scale problems.
- GNNs can easily operate and generalize over environments with a changing topology and a variable number of nodes.

To predict the throughput in IEEE 802.11 WLANs that support DCB, we propose a novel approach, using a Graph Neural Network (GNN) architecture. GNNs are Neural Networks (NNs) that operate on data represented as graphs and exploit the relationship among nodes embedded in the graph's topology. Under GNNs, a graph is defined as a 2-tuple $G = (V, E)$ with V representing a set of nodes with cardinality N and E representing the set of edges with cardinality L . Each node has associated a set of features, represented by a vector of $1 \times D$, where D is the number of input features per node. Similarly, each edge represents the interactions among nodes; their associated features are represented by a vector of the form $1 \times R$ where R is the number of input features per edge. The graph's topology is represented by a binary adjacency matrix of $N \times N$, where a one represents an edge between nodes. Therefore, each deployment is considered as an undirected graph where STAs and APs are the graph's nodes. Position, channel configuration and device type are considered to be the node features. The graph's edges are established, according to the wireless interactions between nodes, e.g., the RSSI received by the AP and the interference levels between BSSs.

We model a WLAN deployment as shown in . The links between STAs and APs represent the connectivity within the BSS through wireless links, while the link between APs represents the interference that BSSs have among themselves. As it can be inferred, APs form a mesh graph, while devices within the BSS form a star-like graph.

Figure 29. Example of a WLAN deployment. On the left, the topological view of the deployment. On the right, the graph representation of the deployment.

Our GNN model uses Graph Convolutional Networks (GCNs) [38], a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) variant operating in graphs. GCN follows a multilayer approach, just like Feed Forward Neural Network (FNN), with the difference that it processes graphs instead of images, time series, or text sequences. The number of Graph Convolutional Layers (GCLs) is typically defined by the diameter of the graph, which tells in how many hops any node is reachable from any other node; so, in this case, the graph diameter is three for inter-BSS interaction (two nodes of different BSS are communicating) and two for intra-BSS interaction (two nodes of the same BSS are communicating). The deployments' topology allows us to consider two GCLs to propagate information from STAs to AP and between APs. Additionally, as a third layer, we use a linear function that operates only on the node's features. All GCLs use REctified Linear Unit (ReLU) as an activation function, and only the first GCL uses dropout for regularization purposes. Figure 30 shows the resulting architecture.

Figure 30. GNN model architecture.

5.2.5 Results

5.2.5.1 Benchmark State-of-the-Art ML models

Two Deep Learning (DL)-based models, a CNN and an FNN, and a Gradient Boost (GB)-based model also were designed to predict the throughput in IEEE 802.11 WLANs that support DCB. The input layer of all models receives the characteristics extracted from the deployment data. However, as each deployment does not have the same number of devices, the data must be processed differently, as these models require a fixed size input. Here, data are pre-processed into a matrix of $N_{DEV} \times D$, where N_{DEV} represents the number of devices in all WLAN deployments and is fed to the models using batches. In turn, the columns (D) represent the device's considered characteristics (e.g., positioning, RSSI and set of bonded channels, among others). At the output layer, the throughput per device is predicted based solely on each device's characteristics.

The CNN uses two 1D convolutional layers, followed by batch normalization and dropout layers to accelerate training and to reduce over-fitting, respectively. Thereafter, three linear layers followed by dropout layers are added. All layers have ReLU activation functions. The FNN consists of four linear layers, the input and output layers, and two additional hidden layers. The number of neurons in the layers follows a decreasing configuration, i.e., 32-16-8-1. The rationale behind this configuration is that at each layer, the most representative data features are extracted. Each layer uses ReLU as activation function, followed by a dropout layer to reduce over-fitting. Lastly, the predicted throughput is obtained at the output layer, configuring a regression model. The architecture of such models is shown in Figure 31.

Figure 31. Architecture of the state-of-the-art models.

The last model is based on Gradient Boost (GB). Boosting algorithms are ensemble methods that minimize the model's loss by adding decision trees, using a gradient descent procedure. In this method, we use default hyper-parameter values, defined by sci-kit learn FNN and GB models are typically used in Wi-Fi performance prediction [32], [33]

5.2.5.2 Dataset

To train the models presented in the sections above, we used the dataset in [39], which was provided in the context of the 2020 edition of the ITU AI/ML for 5G Challenge. The simulated data set was generated using Komondor [40], an IEEE 802.11ax-oriented open-source network simulator that was conceived as a cost-effective simulation tool for studying the performance of novel features, such as DCB or Spatial Reuse (SR) in dense scenarios. As shown in [41], important features in Komondor, such as the Distributed Coordination Function (DCF) operation and DCB, were validated against ns-3 [42] and the well-known Bianchi and Markov models [26], [43].

The data set is divided into two sets, i.e., training and testing. In both cases, enterprise-like scenarios containing a different number of APs and STAs applying DCB are generated, thus depicting multiple situations that could be used for training ML models. The topology of these enterprise-like scenarios is composed of a building floor of a given size (e.g., map size), which is divided in equal-sized offices. The APs' positioning is fixed, while the STAs are randomly placed around the AP's coverage area. Such a topology setting is typically adopted in the simulation scenarios provided by IEEE 802.11 task groups [44]. The data set includes useful information about each deployment, such as the obtained throughput, the RSSI, the airtime in each channel, the interference among devices, or the SINR.

Regarding the DCB configuration, each BSS can use up to $N = 8$ basic non-overlapping channels of 20MHz in the 5 GHz band. Compliant with the 11ax amendment, a given transmitter can bond channels of width 20MHz, 40MHz, 80MHz, and 160MHz, thus leading to channelization $\mathcal{C} = \{\{1\}, \{2\}, \dots, \{8\}, \{1-2\}, \{3-4\}, \dots, \{7-8\}, \{1-4\}, \{5-8\}, \{1-8\}\}$, for basic channels indexed from 1 to 8 (see Figure 27). In each simulated deployment of the data set, both the primary and the total channel width are selected randomly. As for the applied DCB policy, the maximum possible channel width is dynamically used, provided that the involved channels were free during at least the point coordination function interframe space (PIFS) period.

5.2.5.3 Numerical evaluation

The models described above were trained on the corresponding data set with a fixed split (80% for training and 20% for validation). Every model uses the Root Mean-Squared Error (RMSE) as a loss function, defined as $RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=0}^N (x_i - \hat{x}_i)^2}{N}}$. The error was obtained across the predictions (\hat{x}_i) compared to the actual results (x_i), where N is the number of devices in the batch. We trained the models on each set of features defined in Table 6 to quantify how they affect the prediction accuracy. This procedure was performed ten times per experiment to observe each model's convergence.

Table 6. Features used per experiment.

Feature	Definition	E1	E2	E3	E4	E5	E6	E7	E8	E9	E10	E11	E12	E13	E14	E15	E16
Node Type	Wireless node type, AP = 0, STA = 1	X	X	X				X	X					X	X	X	
x(m)	x-coordinate of the wireless node	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	
y(m)	y-coordinate of the wireless node	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	
Channel Configuration	Combination of Primary, minimum and maximum channel	X		X	X							X	X	X	X	X	
SINR	Signal to Interference plus Noise Ratio	X	X			X										X	

Airtime	Percentage of time each AP occupies each of the assigned channels (mean)	X	X	X	X			X		X	X	X	X				X
Interference	Inter-AP interference sensed from every AP (mean)	X		X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X			X
RSSI	Received Signal Strength Indicator	X	X					X	X	X							X
Distance	Euclidean distance between AP and STAs	X	X					X	X			X					X
Bandwidth	Maximum channel bandwidth	X		X	X							X	X	X	X	X	

The testing data set also includes several deployments in enterprise-like scenarios with same channel configurations. However, changes regarding the training data set, including map size, deployment size, and each deployment's user density, were introduced. As a baseline for all ML approaches, we use a random guesser. We assume that the throughput can be obtained from a truncated normal distribution using as the mean and the standard deviation, the ones found in the dataset. This random approach represents a naive and cheap way to generate predictions in this problem.

The trained models were used to predict the throughput of all devices in the test data set. Figure 32 shows the mean RMSE across all test scenarios' deployments in a given experiment for all the generated models and its standard deviation. The standard deviation in all models is very low, having a maximum of 0.66 in the FNN. As can be seen from the figure, GNN outperforms all other approaches in all defined experiments. The random approach performs the same, independent of the features used. Regarding the other ML models, it can be seen that learning from data represents at least a 20% improvement regarding the random approach, using all trainable features (E1). Focused on E1, i.e., the experiments with all features, GNN can obtain up to 64%, 56%, 55%, and 54% when comparing it against the random approach, the CNN, the FNN, and the GB, respectively. Surprisingly, GB performs slightly better in several experiments when compared to the CNN and the FNN. Despite its complexity, the CNN does not perform better than the FNN and the GB. This poor performance might be due to data representation. CNNs outperform other ML approaches when dealing with high-dimensional data (e.g., images, time-series). Even though the wireless environment is too complex to be modeled, the provided data do not include an extra dimension (e.g., time) that CNN can benefit from.

Figure 32. Mean and standard deviation of the obtained RMSE by all models on the test data set.

In some experiments (e.g., E5, E6, E8, E13, E14, and E15), the random guesser performs better than some ML approaches since the combination of input features does not benefit from the learning process. In fact, the Gaussian assumption works well in some cases, and it is widely adopted in many communications aspects. Moreover, the random guesser performs the same, independent of the input features, while for some experiments, the ML approaches benefit from certain features (e.g., E1, E2). This

random guesser includes some basic information and performs better than a best-effort approach. It serves as an upper bound to the ML approaches, as it shows if the ML model is learning.

In terms of feature relevance, including airtime, there is a strong improvement to the results of all ML models. For instance, the only difference between E1/E7 and E15/E8 is that the latter does not consider airtime while the former does. It can be seen that not considering airtime represents between 85% and 87% decrease for the GNN, while other ML approaches perform even worse than the random approach. Nonetheless, considering only airtime as an input feature does not ensure good performance. For example, in E16, GNN decreases its performance by more than 100% regarding E1, except for other ML approaches, where using airtime as an input feature performs even better than considering the rest of the features (see E15).

Analyzing other features, RSSI and distance give more information about the throughput than SINR, node type, and interference. For instance, in E9 and E10, all models improve their performance by including RSSI: 48%, 5%, 10%, and 6% in the GNN, GB, CNN, and FNN, respectively. Similarly, in E11 and E12, GNN obtains around 26% improvement, while CNN and GB obtain 2.4% and 7.5% improvement, respectively, when considering the distance. Interestingly, the GNN is the only model in which features such as node type (E3 vs. E4) and SINR (E5 vs. E6) are relevant and improve its performance. Even when considering interference (E13 vs. E14), a factor that seems to decrease other ML models' performance, GNN obtains a 5% improvement.

5.2.6 Conclusion

Future wireless networks will be highly dense and will require higher performance than what we have today. To address such an increasing complexity, Artificial Intelligence (AI)/ML plays an essential role in modeling and driving wireless networks' behavior. In this contribution, we focused on the performance prediction problem for next-generation WLANs, applying CB techniques, which underlying complexity has, until now, hindered the utilization of analytical models. By replacing such analytical models with ML-based ones, a Wi-Fi controller can accurately evaluate different configurations in a short timescale. Note that ML-enabled spectrum optimization would require less time to perform a prediction when compared to a traditional model (e.g., Markov model), reducing the service response time (K8). Moreover, the spectrum usage can be optimized by using an enhanced view of the network resources and the aid of ML-based performance prediction, improving the management decisions of Wi-Fi controllers (K5).

For that purpose, we propose a GNN model that adapts well in graph-based problems that exhibit combinatorial behavior. Additionally, we compared our GNN model to more traditional ML models and analyzed the impact of different features on the model's performance. Depending on the available data, a controller might use a trained model with a given set of features or another. According to the evaluation, our GNN approach can obtain a 64% increase in the performance regarding a naive approach and around 55% for other ML approaches when using all training features. More details can be found in [45].

5.3 Energy aware edge resource management

The solutions considered in this section intend to contribute to the KPIs K1 (VNF energy consumption reduction) and K2 (Saving of computational resources at the edge). One of the primary aims of the works presented in this section is related with understanding the impact on energy consumption of the different alternative configurations of VNFs, even in colossal configuration spaces where all the measurements are not available, contributing mainly to the reduction of energy consumption (K1). Another important goal addressed in this section was the definition of algorithms/solutions that support the configuration of chained VNFs at the edge to both adapt the VNFs resource requirements to the available Edge resources and to discover new nodes meeting VNFs resource demands. These solutions apply to both the reduction of energy consumption (K1) and the saving of computational resources (K2). A more in-depth revision of related literature can be found in Section 9.4.1.

5.3.1 The problems

The virtualization of network functions allows a better management and scalation of network capabilities on demand using virtual software-based applications where physical boxes once stood in the network architecture. This makes it easier to load-balance, scale up and down, and move functions across distributed hardware resources without interruption to their customers. However, understanding the energy consumption of VNFs in the context of B5G and Edge computing environments is a complex task. The hardware and software elements that influence the energy footprint of a system are characterized by high variability. Indeed, VNFs can be deployed in heterogeneous physical nodes or network equipment and can be allocated inside different kinds of software infrastructure, like virtual machines. This variability is present at different levels such as the service level, the physical level, the network level, or the software infrastructure level. Moreover, focusing on the network level, VNFs also present important levels of variability. For instance, if we think on a security-related VNF, which uses sign and cypher services, its energy consumption will depend on many different configuration factors, such as the physical node

in which the function is running, the crypto provider being used, the selected cryptographic primitives, the security level being provided (i.e. the key size, mode and padding used with those primitives), and even the size of the message being encrypted [46].

One way to cope with the variability problem is to formally represent this variability using *Variability Models* (VMs) [47]. VMs reflect the variability of a system as a set of features and the relationships and constraints among them [47]. Once the variability is modeled, there are tools that take these models as input allowing the analysis of the variants and the automatic generation of valid configurations. But, to reason about the quality attributes (QAs) of these configurations (e.g., performance, energy consumption), these VMs need to be enriched with additional information that allows to relate the values of these QAs (e.g., energy in Joules) with the different features or variants in the model (e.g., the impact of using a variant of the security VNF that uses the AES encryption algorithm with a 512-key size). This is a difficult problem for any system and QA, but it is especially challenging for VMs representing the heterogeneity of edge-based network configurations and for the energy consumption QA.

In summary, VNF and Edge computing bring about highly configurable systems, with thousands of options and complex constraints among them, leading to large configuration spaces. But, for large configuration spaces it is not affordable to manually build and measure the energy consumption of every configuration. Often, neither we could use a single measuring tool (e.g., they are specific for a specific hardware or operating system), nor these tools or devices are always locally available [48]. In addition, energy estimation requires specific expertise and a lot of time and resources, therefore it is considered a hard task. Moreover, energy consumption imposes concrete requirements that makes it different from other QAs because: (1) it is not possible to calculate the energy of a configuration by the simple addition of isolated features consumption, due to the dependencies between different parts of the model (e.g., compression service always consumes 0.8 Joules). Instead, energy needs to be measured at the configuration level, and (2) understanding energy-consumers and interactions by predicting absolute values it is impossible since there are many external factors (e.g., temperature) that can influence the energy consumption and can introduce inaccuracies [48].

5.3.2 Understanding energy consumption

When the configuration space is extremely large and network services developers can measure the energy consumption of only a subset of these configurations, we need an interactive and statistical approach to provide energy consumption insights based on directly accessible measurements. Those energy consumption measurements are traditionally collected from previous experimentations of VNFs running on different Edge devices and environments. Thus, the goal of the algorithm presented in this subsection is to discover those features of VNFs deployed in Edge environments that strongly influence the energy consumption. This algorithm/tool makes use of a selection of sampling, machine learning and statistical techniques.

The approach is named SAVRUS (Smart Analyser of Variability Requirements of Unknown Spaces) and its main objective is to guide in the optimization of edge computing system deployments by identifying the specific features with a high probability to improve the energy consumption if they are replaced by their alternatives. The main novelty of this approach is that it smartly combines methods for analysing configuration spaces, considering large VM with scattered quality measures obtained from unknown domains. It never relies on domain knowledge like training samples or specific on-demand measurements.

5.3.2.1 Approach Overview

The approach overview is shown in Figure 33, which consists of 8 sequential steps numbered from left to right. Steps 1 and 2 are data and user inputs (i.e., the variability model of a VNF, including its internal service functions, and the energy measurements available); steps 3 to 7 are the analysis strategy, and step 8 is the final report.

Figure 33. SAVRUS approach overview highlighting meaningful components

Going into details, step 1 represents the configurable system (i.e., the VM of one or several VNFs), linked with some QA measurements. These measurements presumably will be less than desired and not uniformly distributed, but this is all that we have since the development team cannot always dedicate enough resources to energy footprint experiments of huge configuration spaces. Step 2 represents the network engineer and virtual service developer inputs, which we can summarise as user requirements (i.e., selected features and quality constraints), the maximum number of samples to consider and other optional parameters to adjust the strategy algorithms. Generally, requirements (e.g., host cloud architecture = OpenStack, network timeout > 8 Seconds, energy consumption \leq 3 Watts) with a higher number of samples would produce better results at runtime cost.

Steps 3-7 represent the SAVRUS strategy. The first part, step 3, is any sampling method. While we detailed probabilistic sampling for domain-unknown analyses, SAVRUS is compatible with most methods like guided, heuristic or solver-based sampling. Continuing, in step 4 we include the k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN) method, which is the most popular regression machine learning strategy [77]. kNN does not learn an underlying prediction model, it instead averages the values of unmeasured configurations based on the k-similar measured ones (i.e., k-closest neighbors). Concretely, kNN calculates an averaged value for the QA unmeasured samples if they are requested by step 3. If all samples are measured, or k-closer samples do not exist, kNN is not necessary (i.e., not executed). Having at this point just QA valued samples, step 5 is a statistical test that identifies which are the noteworthy and noticeably interacting features affecting a QA based on the sample set data. The notion of noteworthy features is coined in [49], [50], [51] where normality tests are used with a threshold of 95% confidence. The identified effects depend on the objective; it could be positive (i.e., improving/maximising a QA), negative (i.e., degrading/minimising a QA), or even more complicated ones (e.g., trade-offs). Next, we use another machine learning method, Transfer Learning (TL), which registers knowledge obtained while solving certain problems and applies it to another similar problem. The TL method in step 6 keeps a dynamic track of each t-wise combination noteworthy confidence scores per QA. This enriches SAVRUS current analyses based on previously detected noteworthy interactions. Hence, in step 7 SAVRUS make use of the updated scores to rank feature combinations – the highest the score/lowest the rank, the strongest is the features-QA interaction. For example, if our objective was to minimise energy consumption, we could set the rank as negatively affecting it. Then, if the CPU of a virtualised network node is at the top of the rank (i.e., rank 1), it must be the first replacement to reduce the energy footprint of the system.

Finally, step 8 is the output, which comprises: (i) an ordered list of features and interactions identified as notably affecting a QA with respect to a goal (i.e., minimising energy consumption); and, (ii) the input VM provided in $\circ 1$ graphically highlighting and numbering features and interactions based on the previous list. While a developer pragmatically uses the list to improve the analysed system, the graphical VM provides an overview of the domain knowledge from the energy consumption point of view.

5.3.2.2 Algorithm

The core of the SAVRUS approach is depicted in Algorithm 1. The calling parameters *Data* and *Input* are steps 1 and 2 respectively. At the same time, *Result* is the ranked list of identified affecting features – the arrow to step 8. In summary, 1, 2, and 8 are part of the front-end. In the back-end, algorithm 1 shows the decision logic taken to analyze configurations and QA measures. The front-end is a web application, whereas the back-end is developed in PHP 8 and a MariaDB 10 SQL database stores the VNFs' measurements. This prototype aimed to support Boolean and numerical configurable features (i.e., numerical VMs).

Lines 1 to 3 correspond to the network analyst constraining the VM (e.g., host cloud architecture = OpenStack) and QA (e.g., energy consumption \leq 3). Considering that those features selection constraint the space, we obtain the number of measured samples

Algorithm 1: SAVRUS domain unknown analysis strategy

Data: Variability Model *VM*, Configurations Quality Measurements *CQMs*, Transfer Learning Scores *TLsS*
Input: Number of Samples *#S*, user Requirements *Rs*, Nearest Neighbour Parameter *K*
Result: Ranked Worst Influencing Features and Interactions

```

1 if Rs then // User constrained the search space
2   | VM  $\leftarrow$  Constraint(VM, Rs);
3   | CQMs  $\leftarrow$  Constraint(CQMs, Rs);
   /* Generate #S valid configurations with a
   solver and a sampling algorithm */
4 Samples = Sampling(VM, CQMs, #S);
   /* Unmeasured quality values are the distanced
   weighted mean of k near measurements */
5 foreach S  $\in$  Samples do
6   | if  $\neg$ S.QualityMeasurement then
7     | | S.QualityMeasurement  $\leftarrow$  KNearestNeighbours(K,S);
8 NoteworthyFeatures  $\leftarrow$  MannWhitneyU(Samples);
   /* Having detected influencing features, we
   analyse their pairs and QAs interactions */
9 foreach F1  $\in$  NoteworthyFeatures do
10  | foreach F2  $\in$  NoteworthyFeatures  $\wedge$  (F1  $\neq$  F2) do
11  | | if PairWiseMannWhitneyU([F1,F2], Samples) then
12  | | | Append(NoteworthyFeatures,[F1,F2]);
   /* Detecting feature interactions imply
   recalculations of their confident scores */
13 UpdateTransferLearningScores(TLsS, NoteworthyFeatures);
14 foreach F  $\in$  NoteworthyFeatures do
15  | F.NotworthinessScore  $\leftarrow$  TLsS.F;
   /* Sort interactions/features by learned score */
Result: SortByScore(NoteworthyFeatures)

```

requested by the analyst in the next line. While we have motivated 5 applicable sampling strategies in Section 4, we aim to discard the ones not offering significant advantages against the rest. Based on [52] and [51], we have chosen Distributed Distance Based Sampling (DDbS) and Statistical Recursive Search (SRS), as they outperform other strategies without compromising runtime. SRS is a random sampling with recursion by fixing statistically meaningful features. On the other hand, with DDbS we select samples based on a configurable distance metric and probability distribution, where diversity is increased by prioritising configurations containing the least frequently sampled features. Considering the need for fast analyses without domain knowledge, we implement them as Clafer solver-based; this implies several solver calls when necessary – DDbS search seeds and loops. For the randomization tasks, used by several methods, we aim to generate a discrete uniform distribution, but with the fast (pseudo-random) procedures used in cryptography services. If the sampling method requests unmeasured samples, we try to calculate QA kNN values in lines 5 to 7. If k-closer neighbors were unavailable, the sample is discarded. Now we collect the common features among the samples greatly affecting the QA. Then, in line 8, we perform a Mann-Whitney U test (MWU) test [53] to check if those features are considered noteworthy (i.e., truly affecting) for a QA against the null hypothesis with a 95% confidence.

At this point, we have the measured sample set and the statistically noteworthy features set. In lines 9 to 12 we perform the same MWU tests but to pair-combinations of the noteworthy features set. Hence, while we are not covering all possible interactions, we potentially identify the most common and meaningful ones affecting a QA with the minimum computer resources. The loop ends with a pairwise noteworthy interacting feature set.

Finishing, we apply TL in lines 13 to 15, specifically the Scores function [54] in the PHP library Rubix ML. We keep track of the interactions confident scores, which are the composed likelihood of features affecting a QA based on the accumulated search spaces.

Technically, they are registered in our QAs database. Clarifying, confident scores run from 0 to 1, meaning never to always statistically affecting a QA respectively. We update the confident scores on each SAVRUS execution by re-adjusting them based on the current interactions set (line 13). We calculate the logarithmic scores as $\langle \text{Score}(P, \text{FPSetNFs}) = \log_p(\text{FPSetNFs}) \rangle$ where P is the uniform probability distribution, *FPSetNFs* is the Forecasted probability of a specific Noteworthy Features or interacting features Set, and *p* is the forecast probability. If the result is positive, it is interpreted as a reward to the forecasted score of the features set, and vice versa for a negative score. If it is the first time running SAVRUS, or the specific VM or QA is new, the confidence scores are set to 0 by default. Having calculated the scores, we now use them to sort the set, creating the ranked list of noteworthy features and interactions affecting a QA. This is the result and output of the algorithm.

5.3.2.3 Proof of concept and evaluation

By now, we have performed a proof of concept of SAVRUS using an Edge computing case study and have evaluated and compared the two implementations of our approach, using DDbS and SRS. The results are shown in Table 7 and discussed below.

Table 7. Details of the quality measured numerical variability models (NVM) used to validate SAVRUS

NVM	Description	#Boolean	#Numericals	Space	QA	#Measurements
Dune	Muti-grid solver	11	3	2.304	Equation solving time	2.304
HSMGP	Stencil-grid solver	14	3	3.456		3.456
HiPAcc	Image processing framework	33	2	13.485		13.485
Trimesh	Triangle mesh library	13	4	239.360		239.360
GEC	Generic edge computing	552	2	$\sim 5.3 * 10^8$	Energy Consumption	132.500

Firstly, we tested SAVRUS with the Generic Edge Computing (GEC) case study – a VM with a large configuration space that we have designed as a representation of a regular IoT/Edge/Cloud system for VNFs. Its main details are shown in the bottom of Table 1. The Clafer chocosolver reasoner generated the $\sim 5.3 * 10^8$ configurations of GEC in 36 hours for a total of 552 Boolean and 2 numerical features with parent-children and cross-tree constraints. GEC search space details are also specified in the last row of Table 1, being the largest space considered to evaluate this work. To approximate GEC study to a real scenario, we performed 132500 different measurements, which account for 0.25% of the total search space – hence partially measured. We found interesting feature interactions and optimization insights, where the hosting Operating System, the running Device, and the network interface were the main culprits of the energy consumption of the system for whatever configuration.

Then, we evaluated and compared the two implementations of our approach (i.e., DDbS and SRS). To prove that SAVRUS results are correct, we required completely measured VMs for a well-known QA. Consequently, we opted to test the accuracy of SAVRUS for the QA runtime as the results are aligned with the QA energy consumption. The models, detailed in Table 1, are: Dune, HSMGP, HiPAcc [55] and Trimesh [56]. To emulate our issues, we purposely removed random chunks of measurements mimicking

the issues of large VMs modelling energy-aware VNFs systems (i.e., randomly spread measurements). To obtain domain unknown configuration spaces with scattered measures, we degrade the data by randomly erasing parts of the VMs measured space. For scalability testing, we increased the number of samples from 25 to 6400.

We validated SAVRUS effectiveness regarding: (i) the quality of the features insights; (ii) the size of the sample sets with respect to the space size; and, (iii) the analyses times. SAVRUS generated a correct ranking of noteworthy features and interactions 80% of the times for every incompletely QA measured model. Regarding SAVRUS performance, the current prototype has a base runtime of 1 minute, taking less than 3 minutes for comprehensible cases and scenarios. Between the two sampling implementations, DDBS was the most balanced alternative due to its speed, accuracy, and scalability, especially for large and complex systems. Anyhow, if the analysis time is not an issue, SRS is the most accurate alternative.

5.3.2.4 Conclusions

Currently, we have developed a SAVRUS prototype and proved its usefulness with a large case study from the domain of Edge computing systems, comprising 554 features and a total of 10^8 legal configurations. This case study didn't consider the variability of VNFs. We plan to apply our approach to reason about the energy consumption of highly variable VNFs required in the context of Augmented Reality applications. Specifically, with an offline SAVRUS analysis we will create a learned energy model which in turn transfers the knowledge to real-time algorithms acting on predictors or heuristics. If the network, functions, services or devices are updated, the energy model will evolve with an extra offline adjustment executing SAVRUS again. We expect to improve the speed and accuracy of real-time and dynamic algorithms. This solution will impact mainly KPI K1.

5.3.3 Combining VNFs at the edge

When the configuration space is extremely large due to the heterogeneity of existing edge-infrastructure, the requirements imposed by VNFs, and the variation of resource availability over time, the estimation or prediction of energy consumption is very complex. With the goal of adjusting the configuration of the VNF requirements and edge-based infrastructure capabilities for a better the estimation of energy consumption, we plan to propose the algorithms/solutions presented in this subsection is to alleviate this task, supporting: (i) resource estimation based on hardware demand, identifying those that strongly affects energy consumption on mobile networks; (ii) the adaptation of VNFs resource requirements to the available Edge resources, trying to allocate the least quantity of resources that fits VNFs demands; and (iii) the discovery of new nodes meeting VNFs resource demands, if the available resources in the current infrastructure are not enough to provide a certain QoS required by VNFs. These algorithms/tools are posed as constraint satisfaction problems. Concretely, they use Z3, a SMT solver [57], to obtain the solutions. Thus, (1) the algorithm of the solver always returns a solution, which guarantees that the deployment is feasible or the impossibility to deploy the application if no solution is found; and (2) a large number of constraints (required to solve the problems at hand) help SMT-solvers to reduce the search space and to find the optimal solution faster. Unlike other solvers (e.g., those based on Mixed Integer Linear/Non-linear Programming) SMT solvers neither restrict the variable types involved in the problem formulation (that are unknown) nor the degree of the equations.

The power consumption of applications (including VNFs) can be differentiated into two main parts in the context of mobile networks: computational and communication power consumption. For wireless communications, the factors that are usually considered as part of the energy consumption are the power transmission and the transmission rate and the amount of data to be transmitted [16]. Regarding computation, there are several factors that can influence power consumption, such as CPU, RAM and disk usage, being the CPU the most influential [58]. In this sense, the values to be determined on the node side are its working frequency and the ratio between its frequency and power consumption. Regarding the application, the values to determine are the number of CPU cycles and/or the number of instructions. When considering instructions, the ratio between the number of instructions and the CPU cycles required for each node must be obtained. Since the number of cycles per instruction will depend on the type of instruction, the above value must be obtained considering different types of instructions.

Regarding the adaptation of VNFs resource requirements to the available Edge resources, the solution proposed is the Application Variability Adaptor (AVA) [59]. This algorithm will be useful to foresee if a given edge infrastructure supports the demands of a set of VNFs. Taking as input a configuration of VNF and a given mobile infrastructure, the algorithm output allows to identify those service functions that have special requirements in terms of mobile infrastructure components. In this scenario, the goal is to support the most VNFs allowed by the current infrastructure as possible without including more nodes or extending their capabilities. The AVA would determine the maximal amount of VNF's service function already supported by the current infrastructure and highlight those that are not, avoiding the deployment of VNFs that the architecture does not support, the waste of resources and the occurrence of unexpected failures.

Equation 1 shows the formalization of the AVA. Concretely, this algorithm maximizes the number of supported features and upper range of the attributes, while minimizing their lower range, and maximizes

the number of supported features. As constraints, the algorithm: (1) checks that the infrastructure supports the features contained in *supported*; (2-3) confirms that the infrastructure supports the maximal and minimal values of each attribute; (4) iterates each clonable service and device, evaluating and returning the maximal capabilities supported by each node of the NFVI in case of executing the service on it). Finally, the supported and non-supported features, and the attribute value range are returned.

$$\begin{aligned}
&\text{Maximize:} && size(s) \\
&&& \forall a \in A : a_{max} \\
&\text{Minimize:} && \forall a \in A : a_{min} \\
&\text{Subject to:} && \forall f \in s : support(N, f, CMCs) && (1) \\
&&& \forall a \in A : support(N, a_{max}, CMCs) && (2) \\
&&& \forall a \in A : support(N, a_{min}, CMCs) && (3) \\
&&& \forall n \in N, c \in R : c \in S \wedge support(n, c, CMCs) \rightarrow \\
&&& \quad capabilities(c, d, CMCs) && (4) \\
&\text{Return:} && s \\
&&& ns = F \setminus s \\
&&& \forall a \in A : (a_{min}, a_{max}) && (1)
\end{aligned}$$

Equation 1. Formalization of the AVA.

Concerning the discovery of new nodes meeting VNFs resource demands, the solution proposed is the New Devices Finder (NDF) [59], required when a service must be provided that is not currently supported by the infrastructure, i.e. the infrastructure must support features that are not currently supported. This means that the edge-based infrastructure considered does not meet VNF service functions demand. In this case, the algorithm, taking as input the VNF configuration, informs about the new nodes required to meet a specific VNF (in terms of location, peripherals, computation capabilities, etc.) This algorithm detects all VNF's requisites non-supported by the current infrastructure configuration, and returns a minimal configuration (i.e., the minimal set of features and minimal value of the attributes) of the minimal set of infrastructure nodes to be acquired and added to the given infrastructure to run the VNFs properly. This algorithm uses the demands of the VNF's service functions not already supported to determine the characteristics of the physical and NFVI nodes needed. To assure the QoS of the VNF (if any) related with user experience and latency, each function service has a maximal execution time associated (i.e., time restriction).

This algorithm performs two different steps. In the first step, it detects the non-supported service functions and instantiates one (provisional) device for each one. In the second step, these provisional devices are combined to construct a set of indispensable devices, while avoiding to include those that are expendable.

Equation 2 formalizes the NDF algorithm. As an input, it receives the full configuration (both software and hardware) of the nodes presented in the infrastructure, the configuration of the VNFs' service functions, and the boolean value *virtualization*. To handle this information, the configured Variability Models are processed, including the nodes in the set N , and all the service functions of the VNFs included in the set S . The set S is then composed by the software components that implement the service functions, which are derived from the full configuration of the VNF variability model, including those clonable service functions defined as part of the set R . As an output, the algorithm returns the minimal set of characteristics required by each new device to support the VNFs configuration given as an input.

$$\begin{aligned}
&\text{Maximize:} && size(s) \\
&\text{Subject to:} && \forall se \in S, n \in N : x_{se,n} \rightarrow se \in S \wedge meets(se, n) && (1) \\
&&& n \in N : se \in S \rightarrow \sum_{se \in S} x_{se,n} se_{RAM} \leq n_{RAM} && (2) \\
&&& n \in N : se \in S \rightarrow \sum_{se \in S} x_{se,n} se_{disk} \leq n_{disk} && (3) \\
&\text{Post processing:} && ns = F \setminus s && (4) \\
&&& provisional = createDevices(ns) && (5) \\
&\text{Return:} && merge(provisional, virtualization)
\end{aligned}$$

Equation 2. Formalization of the NDF algorithm

5.3.3.1 Proof of concept and evaluation

By now, we have applied the AVA and NDF to a real case of an academic campus where several devices, those typical of CPSs, are geographically distributed serving different applications. The campus infrastructure includes sensing units, IoT gateways, computers, cloudlets, and dedicated cloud servers, scattered across the campus. These devices are not using all their computation and communication capacities (or even are suspended most of the time). All of them are located at the far edge of the Internet, connected to the campus institutional access network. Both algorithms were able to obtain an optimal solution for their given problems in the case study.

The time needed by our modules to provide a solution varies according to the size of the problem [60]. For this reason, we have evaluated the execution time for different problem sizes. With this purpose, we have developed a Benchmark version of the algorithms, which allows setting the number of features and devices in case of the AVA and the number of services and devices for the NDF. Each experiment is performed 30 times on one thread of an AMD Ryzen 7 1700X processor.

In all the experiments the infrastructure considered is formed by 30 different devices with arbitrary characteristics (set on each experiment). These random characteristics involve software and hardware components, as well as the location. Table 8 shows the results.

Table 8. Algorithms' execution time

Problem size:											
AVA: (D/F)		30/10	30/20	30/30	30/40	30/50	30/60	30/70	30/80	30/90	30/100
NDF: (D/S)											
AVA	Mean (s)	0.07	0.14	0.24	0.41	0.60	0.88	1.39	1.99	2.95	4.23
	Std	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.03
NDF	Mean (s)	0.12	0.50	1.09	1.97	3.03	4.49	6.03	7.94	10.11	12.21
	Std	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.07	0.06	0.06	0.16	0.30

D: Devices. F: Features. S: Services-

For the first algorithm (AVA) the number of features has been incremented up to 100. Experiments show that the AVA returns a solution almost instantaneously in most cases, requiring around 4.2 seconds in the worst case of a very big application formed by 100 heterogeneous features.

Regarding the experiments of the NDF, the number of services has been incremented from 10 to 100. Services characteristics such as computational load, data to transmit, location requirements, type of device, peripherals, sensing units, operating system and interaction ways have been randomly set for each experiment. Results show that, for an application formed by 10 different services, the NDF needs around 0.12 seconds to return a solution, being 12.2 seconds in the worst case of an application formed by 100 different services.

5.3.3.2 Conclusions

The utility of the AVA and NDF is shown by applying them to manage the evolution of an application and the infrastructure of a real IoT scenario [59]. The execution time of our algorithms for different problem sizes has been also evaluated using a *Benchmark*, and the conclusion is that they return a solution in a reasonable amount of time. These solutions will have an impact on both KPIs K1 and K2.

5.4 Data-driven resource orchestration

5.4.1 Motivation

Today, the fastest growing mobile device category is Machine-to-Machine (M2M) or Internet of Things (IoT) devices (e.g., wearables, connected cars or smart meters), followed by smartphones. Overall, considering both cellular and fixed line connectivity, the M2M connections will be half of the global connected devices and connections by 2023, with connected cars representing the fastest growing application type (The Cisco Annual Internet Report, 2020). In this context, M2M platforms have a central role in supporting this type of IoT applications. These latter benefit from international roaming and the extensive global network infrastructure that international carriers (e.g., incumbent tier-one operators such as Vodafone, Tata, Telefónica or Orange) have been shaping for the past decades. In this context, the exponential growth of roaming IoT is key for Mobile Network Operators (MNOs), as it could lead to increased stress on the infrastructure shared with traditional traffic. Managing the growing stress of M2M communication would not be a new problem for MNOs, if M2M traffic showed similar characteristics to that of phone traffic (and brought comparable revenues). However, M2M traffic exhibits significantly different features than phone traffic in a range of aspects from signaling, to uplink/downlink traffic volume ratios to diurnal patterns. In other words, though these devices occupy radio resources in MNOs

networks and exploit the MNOs interconnections in the cellular ecosystem, they do not generate traffic that would allow MNOs to accrue revenue.

We currently expect a complex mix of applications and communication types in 5G networks: Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Massive Machine-Type Communication (mMTC), ultra-Reliable and Low Latency (uRLLC). The last two are, in fact, Internet of Things (IoT) applications, which we know as Massive IoT with low cost and low power devices, and Critical IoT, known for their latency and reliability stringent requirements. They are diverse in many aspects, such as data consumption, bandwidth requirements, the density of devices, and mobility. However, we are now coming into an era where we have a combination of these applications, and devices generate different traffic types. The rise of multimedia IoT (M-IoT) can also add to the complexity of the ecosystem, since delay-sensitive and high bandwidth multimedia streams challenge low-capacity IoT devices (e.g., low memory storage, CPU, energy). Moreover, support for "things" roaming internationally has become critical for IoT verticals, from connected cars to smart meters and wearables, and explains the commercial success of Machine-to-Machine (M2M) platforms.

For operators, the exponential growth of IoT (and its massive and heterogenous set of connected devices) has meant increased stress on the infrastructure shared with traditional smartphone traffic. Furthermore, the commercial success of M2M platforms impacts the visited Mobile Network Operators (MNOs), who are offering connectivity to a wide range of foreign devices, operating as inbound roamers. To manage the impact of massive deployments of device operating with a (at time roaming) IoT SIM, operators must be able to distinguish between the latter, traditional inbound roamers, and native (local) IoT devices and smartphones. However, little effort has gone into empirically characterizing the behavior of device population connecting to the radio network of an MNO.

Our goal is to develop novel algorithms and solutions based on these new concepts of cellular networks to support M-IoT application requirements. M-IoT applications are classified into five categories of Connected Cars, Smart Cities, Connected Health, Connected Industry, and Connected Living and Working. That is why as a starting point, to recognize the demands of these applications, we have studied Connected Cars as a use case in this deliverable. Then, we will focus on devising learning-based resource management techniques to meet these requirements. Moreover, learning algorithms can be leveraged to predict near-future traffic patterns, and such predictions enable proactive and accurate resource management decisions. The main focus in this project will be a data-driven design, development, implementation and experimentation of radio resource management algorithms.

5.4.2 Dataset description

The cellular network we study supports 2G, 3G, 4G and 5G mobile communication technologies. In Figure 34, we illustrate a high-level schema of the MNO architecture. Such a network can be simplified to consist of three main domains: (i) the cellular device (in our case, the smart meter), (ii) the Radio Access Network (RAN), and (iii) the Core Network (CN). Our passive measurement approach relies on commercial solutions integrated within the MNO's infrastructure. The red pins in Figure 34 mark the network elements that we monitor, namely the Mobility Management Entity (MME), the Message Sequence Chart (MSC) and the Serving GPRS Support Node (SGSN). We collect control plane data on the total population of devices connected to the MNO's radio network. This includes both native devices (operating with a SIM card provisioned by the UK MNO) or inbound roaming devices (operating with a SIM card provisioned by a foreign MNO, from outside the UK, such as the global IoT SIM provided by the M2M platform).

We start introducing the raw data collected by the operator, and then we discuss how we label devices based on their roaming category, and how we identify IoT devices.

Radio interfaces. We process logs reporting on activities on LuCS, LuPS, A, and Gb radio interfaces. Those carry events generated by the devices connecting to the radio sectors, and requesting resources for either data or voice communications. Each event carries the anonymized user ID, SIM MCC and MNC, Type Allocation Code (TAC)³, the sector ID handling the communication, timestamp, event type, event result code. Such events are captured for all connected devices, except for outbound roamers (in this case, radio signaling for outbound roamers is carried over the visited country network only).

Service usage. We use Call Detail Records (CDRs) and eXtended Detail Records (xDRs) to provide aggregate service usage for calls and data. Each record reports the anonymized user ID, MCC, and MNC codes for both device SIM and visited country, timestamp, duration, and bytes consumed. Data records also report APN strings, which usually encode information about the specific service/business they relate to. Notice that differently from radio logs, CDRs/xDRs contain traffic also for outbound roamers. These are usually used by the roaming partners to trigger the process of revenue retrieval from roaming.

Device properties. We also consider a commercial database provided by GSMA. This catalog maps the device TAC to a set of device properties such as device manufacturer, brand and model name, operating system, and radio bands supported.

Figure 34. MNO monitoring approach.

Daily devices-catalog. We combine the three data sources to create a daily list of active devices and associated properties and traffic characteristics. We refer to this aggregate view as devices-catalog. Each record reports a device ID, total number of events, calls, bytes seen, SIM MCC/MNC, list of visited MCC-MNC, a list of APN strings, device manufacturer, device model, device Operating System (OS). We summarize the radio activity into radio-flags, a series of three 1-bit flags which are set to 1 if the device has successfully communicated with 2G, 3G, 4G sectors respectively on radio interfaces. Finally, we compute mobility metrics for each device; namely, we calculate the gyration, which captures the distance devices travel throughout a day.

Roaming Labels. To capture the roaming status of the MNO's population, we label each device as either native, inbound roamer, or outbound roamer. A device is native if it carries an MNO's SIM and connects to that same MNO's radio network. When such devices connect to a different operator network (either within the same country, or when traveling outside the country) they become outbound roamers (national or international, respectively). Conversely, an inbound roamer is a device operating with a SIM card not belonging to the MNO whose radio network is actually using. To capture these variants, we tag each record in the devices catalog with a roaming label <X:Y>, where X relates to the device SIM, and Y to the visited network. Specifically, given a SIM card, we assign to X four possible values: H (home, the SIM belongs to the MNO we analyse), V (virtual, the SIM belongs to an MVNOs enabled by the MNO we analyse), N (national, the SIM belongs to another MNO in the same country as the current MNO), I (international, the SIM belongs to an MNO in a country different than the one of the MNO under study). Instead, we assign to Y only two values: H (home, the SIM is attached to the current MNO), A (abroad, the SIM is attached to a foreign MNO outside the country of the MNO under study).

Overall, we define 6 different roaming labels. For example, the H:H label reflects a device that uses the MNO's SIM card and is attached to the MNO's network (i.e., native user), while the I:H label refers to devices connected to the MNO under study but with a SIM of operators of different countries than the MNO one (i.e., inbound roamers). Using these labels, we further breakdown devices per roaming status. As expected, we find that the majority of devices are native, i.e., either MNO (about 48% per-day) or MVNO (about 33% per-day) devices connected to their home MNO. However, we find that the third largest population is international inbound roamers (about 18% per-day).

M2M/IoT Device Classification. As previously mentioned, the devices-catalog includes all devices connected to the MNO network. This encompasses devices used by people as their main personal device (e.g., smartphones, feature phones), as well as devices IoT verticals use to support their applications (e.g., car manufacturers, energy companies). Supporting our analysis from the point of view of the M2M platform (§ 3), we aim to establish whether IoT devices are usually roaming internationally. To do so, we split the devices into three classes: smart (for smartphones), feat (for feature phones), and m2m (for IoT/M2M devices). Prior work [21] demonstrated that using device properties one can perform classification, especially to spot M2M devices, at the cost of some manual verification. The GSMA database already offers a device classification label, but devices other than smartphones are mostly marked as "modem" or "module" which might not necessarily imply an M2M/IoT application. Furthermore, across the data we collect over 22 days in April of 2019, we observe 2,436 device vendors, and 24,991 device models across the whole population (i.e., a manual classification as operated in [21] is not feasible).

One possible approach to reduce the classification complexity is to focus on “big players” only. For instance, Gemalto, Telit, and Sierra Wireless are among the top device vendors with a combined 75% of all roaming devices in the dataset. Similar considerations can be made to identify smartphones and feature phones, but we argue that this is a naïve approach as still requires to investigate a large number of devices to validate the classification.

APNs string can be a significant aid for strengthening the confidence of the classification as they hint the vertical used by a device. For instance, “*smhp.centricapl.com.mnc004.mcc204.gprs*” hints to Centrica, a company working in the energy vertical, i.e., the devices using such APN are possibly smart meters. Notice also the MCCMNC revealing the home country and operator (20404 = Vodafone Netherlands). We find a total of 4,603 APN strings in the dataset. However, ranking the APNs by number of devices using it, we identified 26 “keywords” in the APN string which we mapped to M2M/IoT verticals using information found online (e.g., scania - automotive company, rwe - energy company, intelligent.m2m - global IoT SIM provider). Using these 26 keywords we obtained 1,719 APNs, while the other are either generic labels related to mobile operators (2,178 labels likely related to consumer services), or other IoT services we could clearly identify.

Finally, we classify the devices combining both APNs and device properties. We start marking as m2m all devices using the validated APNs. Then, we extend the m2m class to all devices having the same properties of the devices using the validated APNs. For *smart* and *feat* we still use a set of APN strings, but we take advantage of 2 labels properties defined in the GSMA database (e.g., device manufacturer, and operating system). Specifically, we classify a device as *smart* if declared to be using a major smartphone OS (android, iOS, blackberry, windows mobile) and use a consumer APN (e.g., a string contain keywords such as “payandgo”). Instead, we classify a device as *feat* if the GSMA database declares it to be a feature phone or uses a consumer APN.

Out of the 39.6M devices active across the 22 days, we find 24.4M (62%) *smart*, 3.1M (8%) *feat*, and 10.1M (26%) *m2m*. We label the remaining 2M (4%) as *m2m-maybe* as the device properties suggest they are neither smartphones nor feature phones, but we don't have APNs for them, i.e., those devices only use voice services (the APN is provided only when the device connect for data services). This does not preclude them from possibly being M2M related, but based on the information available we are not able to provide a final classification. Hence, we do not consider those devices for the remainder of the analysis. Using APNs is useful to increase the classification confidence, and reduce the number of manual investigations. However, when used in isolation, APNs are not enough as we find about 21% of the devices in the dataset not having any APN. This justifies our multi-steps classification process (keywords → APNs → device properties).

5.4.3 Device Population Profiles

So far, we have been analyzing connected car characteristics, mobility patterns, and data usage based on UK mobile network operator's (MNO) datasets. Raw data has been collected by the MNO in GPDR compliance, to ensure there are no identifiers to people; also, all analysis report is based on aggregated metrics. Our datasets provide a comprehensive view of the devices connected to the MNO for two weeks in early 2020. We focus here on three categories, namely connected cars, smartphones, and other IoT devices based on Access Point Name (APN) strings and device properties. Our sample of connected cars includes approximately 400,000 different devices installed in vehicles from ten car manufacturers.

First, we investigate whether these devices are different in terms of device adoption and properties. The average lifespan (based on the release date not the production) of connected cars, smartphones, and other IoT devices are 5.96, 3.02, 5.56, respectively. Regardless, it is smaller than the mean age of industrial IoTs, and connected cars that [1, 10] observed, it corroborates previous remarks in respect of the order. Figure 35 (a) shows radio connectivity technologies for each device class. We observe that ≈49% of cars support 4G capability, with the share of ≈27% 2G only, and without 5G-enabled cars in 2020. Whereas about 95% and almost 0.03% of smartphones are 4G,5G capable, respectively (5G not shown), and only 28% of other IoT devices support 4G. Accordingly, although 4G penetration is higher among cars (industrial IoT was 2% [61]), discontinuing 2G will affect connected cars as significantly as on other IoT devices. Furthermore, we observe cars have supported 4G connectivity since 2014, whereas 4G-enabled smartphones have been around since 2009, and more than half of the smartphones produced in 2012 were 4G capable. There is at least a 2-year gap here, which points out that we cannot expect cars are supporting 5G in the very near future. Hence, network management algorithms and optimizations for IoT applications should continue to improve on the legacy technologies, and even if they target 5G, they should also be backward compatible.

In Figure 35 (b) we compare the daily per user traffic of connected cars to the remaining IoT and smartphone users. To guarantee data confidentiality, we normalize the plots by the maximum value. Smartphones still generate the majority of traffic transferring on mobile networks. However, we can see a clear difference between connected cars and other IoT devices, which will become broad by the increasing multimedia application in cars. Then, we analyze the number of radio management signaling events per user of each type of device in Figure 35 (c). Smartphones trigger significantly more events

than other devices; On average, 6 and 11 times comparing to connected cars and other IoT, respectively. It could be explained by their high mobility and activity on the network. Connected cars are also mobile, yet they spend less time connected to the network and thus generate a lower number of signals. On the other hand, IoT devices are often stationary, and thus they generate little signaling traffic. Overall, these indicate a particular need for network management methods not only for the IoT but also for each vertical separately.

Figure 35. Comparison among devices: connected cars, other IoT verticals, and smartphones.

Figure 36. Car Brands Comparison; figures show diurnal per car values, log scaled, and normalized.

In addition, we find out that different cars do not behave in the same way either. In this regard, we consider a sample of the top 6 connected car brands, which includes most cars in our dataset. First, we explore radio technology of the cars. While $\approx 78\%$ of brand 1 are 4G-enabled, $\approx 71\%$ of brand 3 are only 2G-capable. Figure 36 further validates our intuition on the diverse behaviors in terms of mobility (a) and signaling (b). Figure 36 (a) presents the average number of distinct cell sectors to which each car connects daily over days. These simply illustrate that we cannot decide about the network resource allocation just based on the group of devices as MNOs do today, and we need more granular network slicing. Another interesting finding of our analysis is that, although about 27% of brand 2 were 4G capable, they were only active on the 2G/3G data interface. Hence, though device capabilities allow for faster data connections, they might never use these, and still depend on the 2G/3G network. This brings the discussion around the 2G/3G network shutdown to our attention once more.

5.4.4 Resource Management Approach.

Given the heterogeneous services the MNO supports across network elements, it is not trivial to use the existing datacenter resource scheduling techniques and translate to requirements we extract from our analysis. For example, Figure 37 shows a deep learning task (Object detection) within an XR application. The variants of the request can be the devices requesting, accuracy and latency requirements of the DL model. Based on these goals and constraints in terms of load spread across the network devices, the decision needs to be made at runtime.

Figure 37. Request scheduling for optimal resource allocation at real time.

To this end, we are building a learning paradigm based on uncertain network dynamics and algorithms that can learn and adapt their environment based on resource availability. We call this Adaptive Scheduling of Edge Tasks (ASET), which runs a smart RL agent trained using real-world network topology and identify the best policy to schedule the workloads in a network the using DRL techniques. The policy can be as simple as executing a task at a closest edge cluster to schedule based on latency and load at real time.

Figure 38. Adaptive Scheduling of Edge Tasks (ASET) workflow.

Our adaptive scheduling approach aims to learn the optimal policy depending on current system conditions, e.g., current applications, network topology, and stream arrivals that vary over time. Due to the lack of labelled data, the optimal policy learning is formulated as a RL problem; hence, an intelligent agent tries to learn the optimal policy selection strategy according to the observed state of the environment. This is accomplished by an RL policy that estimates a probability distribution of each possible action (policy selection) that cumulatively maximizes a reward (typically maximizing the fraction of queries that are served successfully), as shown in Figure 38.

Figure 39. Percentage of successful queries over time for ML task with users arriving in real-world pattern.

Initial results (Figure 39. Percentage of successful queries over time for ML task with users arriving in real-world pattern.) suggest, even with partial view of the network resources, ASET performs better than traditional scheduling mechanisms. We simulate the scenario of users arriving in real-world pattern. The work is still on-going to implement better selection of policies through multi-agent communication, security & privacy-aware and real-world deployments.

Furthermore, we envisage to integrate the scheduler with AIRO to render both smart orchestration and scheduling for XR applications facilitating cloud-edge continuum.

5.5 Multi-timescale network slice reservation

5.5.1 Motivation

The problem of network slicing optimization is motivated by the increasing softwarization of wireless networks coupled with the emerging complex interaction between over-the-top service providers (SPs) and network operators' infrastructure (NOs), where SPs rely on the equipment of the latter in their operation. In this section, we introduce our contribution in studying the problem of deciding the optimal amount of network resources' slices from the perspective of SPs [62].

Network slicing markets (Figure 40. Network slicing markets. SPs reserve resources from operators' equipment with the aim of maximizing efficiency in their services) are inspired by cloud computing marketplaces, where cloud providers adapt their offered prices dynamically, and SPs complement their reservations with real-time bidding in spot markets. Such flexibility renders challenging the task of SPs. Effectively, SPs need to decide on slice reservations (i.e., request resources) without knowing the needs of their users and also to choose between (lower-cost) advance reservations and (higher-cost) on-the-fly reservations. SPs might suffer the undesirable costs of network over/underutilization of these decisions are ineffective.

Figure 40. Network slicing markets. SPs reserve resources from operators' equipment with the aim of maximizing efficiency in their services.

Common in most of the existing literature is the (often strong) assumptions on users' demand patterns. The approach we seek here does not assume known (distribution of) users' demands and is a one that deduces reservation policy that performs as well as the best one in hindsight despite the NO's (potentially arbitrary) pricing decisions. This is mainly done through online convex optimization (OCO) [63] techniques. The slice reservation problem intrinsically requires decision-making at different time scales. We explicitly model this requirement in our model and study its implications.

5.5.2 System model and problem formulation

The online optimization of network slice reservation, from the perspective of SPs, is modeled considering the following characteristics:

- Mixed-time scale online decision making: We tackle the problem in an online manner and at two different time scales: a larger one which we call "period", and a more fine-grained scale called "slots". A period consists of one or more slots, e.g., days and hours. At the beginning of each period, the SP decides on the number of slice units to be reserved during the period as well as slots based on the history of its observation (and without knowing or assuming anything about the future prices or users' demands/utilities). The slots-level decision can be modified in response to the evolving pricing data.
- Unknown prices for slice units at the two different time scales: The reservations and spot prices are revealed one-by-one after and action (i.e., slice unit selection) are committed, and the only information available to the SP before this decision is the historical ones.
- Our aim: We aim to learn a policy that maximizes a utility function (benefits minus costs style of function) in hindsight (i.e., we aim to match, asymptotically, a hypothetical reservation policy that is calculated assuming full knowledge of the future). This is captured through the "regret", and constraints violation metrics:

$$R_T = \sum_{t=1}^T (f_t(x_t, \mathbf{y}_t) - f_t(x_t^*, \mathbf{y}_t^*)) , \quad V_T = \max(0, \sum_{t=1}^T (g_t(x_t, \mathbf{y}_t)))$$

Where x_t are the decisions at the larger time scale (i.e., period reservation), and \mathbf{y}_t is a vector of the slot-level decisions.

The objective function $f_t(x_t, \mathbf{y}_t)$ is defined as $-\sum_{k=(t-1)K+1}^{tK} a_k \log(x_t + \mathbf{y}_k + 1)$ (i.e., using log utility), where K is the number of time slots. And the budget constraint function is $g_t(x_t, \mathbf{y}_t) = x_t p_t + \mathbf{y}_t \mathbf{q}_t - B \leq 0$,

5.5.3 Proposed solution and evaluation

We rely on the theory of online convex optimization. Specifically, we execute the FTRL algorithm on a Lagrangian function that we design and show converges to a no-regret policy and no-violations. This means that with time, the difference between the learned online slice period reservation policy and that of the best in hindsight diminishes to zero. We also show experimentally that we can revise the spots' decisions (i.e., the decision at the smaller timescale), achieving better results. The mechanics of a decision step is shown in Figure 41.

Figure 41. A step in the online decision making framework.

For simulation experiments, a slicing market with the following properties is considered: the NO manages B cellular base stations connected through a backhaul network of 100 paths to N = 20 core nodes. Thus, SP reserve slices with the following four resources: wireless and backhaul bandwidth, storage, and CPU capacity. The maximum slice size of D units is determined by the most scarce of these resources. The simulation is done under two different pricing/utility models: uniformly random and a non-stationary stochastic process. The main results on regret and constraints violations are shown in Figure 42. We observe the expected behavior of convergence to zero in the regret case and maintaining a negative (or zero) constraints value (i.e., constraints are satisfied).

Figure 42. Regret and violation convergence with Budget B=10, and slots (i.e., smaller time scale) = 5.

- The second experiment is related to the mixed-time scale decision making. Here, we allow the policy to change the "slots" decisions while within the same period, and we call it Online Learning for Reservation – Mixed Time Scale (OLR-MTS). Recall that in OLR the slots decisions are committed at the beginning of the period. Figure 43 compares the performance of both policies and for different values of the K (slots per period). We observe the improved performance for the MTS variant, especially for the first case, since the SP updates its decisions as new information becomes available. Both variants maintain satisfactory regret violations.

Figure 43. Regret and violations convergence in different mixed-scale setups.

5.5.4 Summary

In this work, we considered the network slice reservation optimization. The problem is modeled as a constrained online mixed-time scale decision-making problem, wherein SPs make reservations before knowing the prices. Utilizing the theory of online convex optimization and extending it to handle long-term budget constraints, we deduced policies with similar performance, asymptotically, to a hypothetical benchmark policy that knows the future prices and users' utilities in all future time slots. Thus, this class of policies is robust to changes of the resource prices, and oblivious to lack of this information at the time of making the online decisions. This contribution supports meeting KPI 4 as the optimized slicing decision for the operator were shown to minimize their cost while maintaining the desired performance.

6 Reconfigurable intelligent surfaces control

Spurred by economic and environmental concerns, the design of energy-efficient high-bandwidth wireless technologies is becoming paramount. Re-configurable Intelligent Surfaces (RISs), which apply controllable transformations into impinging radio waves without leveraging on power amplifiers, create a host of opportunities for the optimization of wireless systems at a low cost and with a low energy footprint. They are in fact gaining a lot of momentum because of their ability to turn the stochastic nature of the wireless environment—fundamentally passive—into a programmable channel that plays an active role on the way in which signals propagate. RISs have been recently proposed for a variety of applications, ranging from secure communications, non-orthogonal multiple access, over-the-air-computation, energy-efficient cellular networks, or to aid mmWave communications [64].

A RIS is essentially a continuous meta-surface that can be modeled as a grid of discrete unit cells spaced at sub-wavelength distance that can alter their electromagnetic response, such as phase, amplitude, polarization and frequency in a programmable manner. For instance, they can be tuned such that signals bouncing off a RIS are combined constructively to increase signal quality at the intended receiver, i.e., perform passive beamforming, or destructively to avoid leaking signals to undesired receivers. Conceptually, a RIS may remind some of the challenges behind conventional Amplify-and-Forward (AF) relaying methods and the beamforming methods used in (massive) MIMO. There exists a marked difference between conventional AF relays and RISs. Indeed, the former rely on active (energy-consuming) low-noise power amplifiers and other active electronic components, such as digital-to-analog (DAC) or analog-to-digital (ADC) converters, mixers and filters. In contrast, RISs have very low hardware footprint, consisting on a single or just a few layers of planar structures that can be built using lithography or nano-printing methods. Consequently, RISs result to be particularly attractive for seamless integration into walls, ceilings, object cases, building glasses or even clothing.

While the reader can find more pointers to the state of the art and the open challenges in Section 9.3, we next discuss the specific problem we addressed in the context of WP3.

6.1 Motivation

Our first goal is to exploit the sum mean squared error (SMSE) as an objective when optimizing jointly a RIS and a mmWave-based transmitter. The choice of an objective function is of paramount importance, especially for massive access scenarios. Our objective function is purposely chosen such that we can derive a mechanism that provides high-performing solutions while guaranteeing efficiency and scalability. Interestingly, such metric reveals a convex structure in the two optimization variables separately, namely the precoding strategy at the transmitter and the RIS parameters. This gives us an edge over prior work because it allows to design very efficient iterative algorithms for RIS control. Specifically, we present RISMA, a RIS-aided Multiuser Alternating optimization algorithm that jointly optimizes the beamforming strategy at the transmitter (a BS) and the RIS parameters to provide high-bandwidth low-cost connectivity. RISMA exploits the convex nature of the problem at hand in the two optimization variables separately to ensure scalability, efficiency and provable convergence in the design without the need of setting any system parameter.

Moreover, we adapt RISMA, which provides a solution from a theoretical perspective, to accommodate practical constraints when using low-resolution RISs that are comprised of antenna elements that can be activated in a binary fashion. In this way, these are meta-surfaces that only support phase shift values from a discrete set, rather than any real value from a range, and further compound our problem. To address this scenario, we propose Lo-RISMA, which decouples the optimization of the binary activation coefficients and the quantized phase shifts. The former are optimized via SDR while the latter are projected onto the quantized space. Differently than other prior work considering low-resolution RISs, Lo-RISMA benefits from the key properties of the chosen SMSE metric. Specifically, for each iteration of the proposed algorithm for a fixed RIS configuration the precoding strategy is found via a simple closed form solution. Whereas once the precoding strategy is fixed the problem of finding the RIS parameters can be efficiently solved via SDR.

6.2 Notation

Throughout this section, we use italic letters to denote scalars, whereas vectors and matrices are denoted by bold-face lower-case and upper-case letters, respectively. We let \mathbb{C} , \mathbb{R} and \mathbb{Z} denote the set of complex, real and integer numbers, respectively. We use \mathbb{C}^n and $\mathbb{C}^{n \times m}$ to represent the sets of n -dimensional complex vectors and $m \times n$ complex matrices, respectively. Vectors are denoted by default as column vectors. Subscripts represent an element in a vector and superscripts elements in a sequence. For instance, $\mathbf{x}^{(t)} = [x_1^{(t)}, \dots, x_n^{(t)}]^\top$ is a vector from \mathbb{C}^n and $x_i^{(t)}$ is its i th component. Operation $(\cdot)^\top$ represents the transpose operator, \otimes stands for Kronecker product while $(\cdot)^H$ denotes the Hermitian transpose operation. Finally, $\|\cdot\|$ and $\|\cdot\|_F$ denote the L2-norm of a vector and Frobenius norm of a matrix, respectively.

6.3 System model

Let us consider the scenario described in Figure 44 in which a BS equipped with M antennas serves a set of K single-antenna user equipment nodes (UEs).

Figure 44. Radio massive access scenario overcoming NLOS issues by means of RISs installed on the building glasses. It might support different use cases, such as AR-glasses, e-health, video-surveillance, Industrial-IoT.

However, note that the proposed method is not limited to such a case. When considering multiple-antenna UEs, our model can be readily applied by letting each UE activate the antenna with the highest average channel power gain. The connection is established with the aid of a set of RISs installed on the building glasses each of which consists of N equivalent antenna elements. Focusing on the downlink data transmission, the BS communicates to each UE k via a direct link denoted by $\mathbf{h}_{d,k} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times 1}$ which comprises of a line-of-sight (LoS) path of length d_k and angle of departure (AoD) θ_k when the latter exists, in addition to a multipath non-line-of-sight (NLoS) link. Additionally, the BS can exploit a combined link from the BS to the RIS denoted by $\mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$, which in turns reflects the incoming signal towards the UE through the channel $\mathbf{h}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$. The latter is decomposed into the LoS BS-RIS path of length $d_{1,k}$ and with AoD from the BS and angle of arrival (AoA) at the RIS denoted by ψ_D and ψ_A , respectively plus a set of scattered NLoS paths and the RIS-UE k link which comprises of a LoS path of length $d_{2,k}$ and AoD θ_k when available, plus a multipath NLoS link. Lastly, due to high path loss we neglect all signals reflected two times or more by the RIS.

All channels follow a quasi-static flat-fading model and thus remain constant over the transmission time of a codeword. We further assume that perfect channel state information (CSI) is available at the BS, i.e., the latter knows $\{\mathbf{h}_{d,k}\}_{k=1}^K$, \mathbf{G} and $\{\mathbf{h}_k\}_{k=1}^K$. The BS operates in time-division duplexing mode, such that the uplink and downlink channels are reciprocal. The downlink physical channel can thus be estimated through the uplink training from the UEs via a separate control channel.

While we focus on the downlink data transmission, our proposed framework might be straightforwardly extended to the uplink direction considering multiple UEs and one single BS. Each UE k receives the sum of two contributions, namely a direct path from the BS and a suitably reflected path upon the RIS. Hence, the receive signal at UE k is given by

$$\begin{aligned} y_k &= (\mathbf{h}_k^H \Phi \mathbf{G} + \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^H) \mathbf{W} \mathbf{s} + n_k \in \mathbb{C} \\ &= (\mathbf{h}_k^H \Phi \mathbf{G} + \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^H) \mathbf{w}_k s_k + \sum_{j \neq k} (\mathbf{h}_k^H \Phi \mathbf{G} + \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^H) \mathbf{w}_j s_j + n_k, \end{aligned}$$

where $\Phi = \text{diag}[\alpha_1 e^{j\phi_1}, \dots, \alpha_N e^{j\phi_N}]$ with $\phi_i \in [0, 2\pi)$ and $|\alpha_i| \leq 1, \forall i$ represents the phase shifts and amplitude attenuation introduced by the RIS (\cdot), $\mathbf{W} = [\mathbf{w}_1, \dots, \mathbf{w}_K] \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times K}$ is the transmit precoder, $\mathbf{s} = [s_1, \dots, s_K]^T \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times 1}$ is the transmit symbol vector with $\mathbb{E}[|s_k|^2] = 1, \forall k$, and n_k is the noise term distributed as $\mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_n^2)$.

Hence, assuming single-user decoding at the receiver side the system sum rate can be defined as follows

$$R \triangleq \sum_k \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{|\mathbf{h}_k^H \Phi \mathbf{G} + \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^H \mathbf{w}_k|^2}{\sum_{j \neq k} |\mathbf{h}_k^H \Phi \mathbf{G} + \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^H \mathbf{w}_j|^2 + \sigma_n^2} \right).$$

Equation 3.

6.4 Problem formulation

Our objective is to optimize the overall system performance of the considered RIS-aided network in terms of the system sum rate, as defined in **Equation 3**. In particular, given the complexity of treating such an expression, we propose to jointly optimize the precoding strategy at the BS and the reflections (as a tunable parameter) introduced by the RIS by minimizing the SMSE over all connected UEs, which is known to relate to the sum rate. In particular, for a given configuration of the RIS the considered system in the downlink is a broadcast channel and duality between broadcast and uplink multiple access channel holds. In the dual multiple access channel the classical relation between minimum mean squared error (MSE) of UE k and maximum SINR of UE k holds for linear filters. Hence, this motivates us to study the SMSE as a means to optimize the system sum rate in the downlink.

The receive MSE of UE k is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \text{MSE}_k &= \mathbb{E}[|y_k - s_k|^2] \\ &= |(\mathbf{h}_k^H \Phi \mathbf{G} + \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^H) \mathbf{w}_k - 1|^2 + \sum_{j \neq k} |(\mathbf{h}_k^H \Phi \mathbf{G} + \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^H) \mathbf{w}_j|^2 + \sigma_n^2 \\ &= \sum_j |(\mathbf{h}_k^H \Phi \mathbf{G} + \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^H) \mathbf{w}_j|^2 - 2 \text{Re}\{(\mathbf{h}_k^H \Phi \mathbf{G} + \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^H) \mathbf{w}_k\} + 1 + \sigma_n^2. \end{aligned}$$

The receive SMSE over all UEs is thus expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{SMSE} &= \sum_k \text{MSE}_k \\ &= \sum_k \sum_j |(\mathbf{h}_k^H \Phi \mathbf{G} + \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^H) \mathbf{w}_j|^2 - 2 \sum_k \text{Re}\{(\mathbf{h}_k^H \Phi \mathbf{G} + \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^H) \mathbf{w}_k\} + K(1 + \sigma_n^2). \end{aligned}$$

For ease of presentation, let us define

$$\mathbf{v} = [\alpha_1 e^{-j\phi_1}, \dots, \alpha_N e^{-j\phi_N}, 1]^T \in \mathbb{C}^{N+1 \times 1},$$

and

$$\bar{\mathbf{H}}_k \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \text{diag}(\mathbf{h}_k^H) \mathbf{G} \\ \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^H \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{C}^{N+1 \times M},$$

such that $\Phi = \text{diag}(\mathbf{v}[1:N]^H)$ and⁶

$$(\mathbf{h}_k^H \Phi \mathbf{G} + \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^H) \mathbf{w}_j = \mathbf{v}^H \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k \mathbf{w}_j \quad \forall k, j.$$

Hence, our optimization problem can be formulated as follows

$$\begin{aligned} &\underset{\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{W}}{\text{minimize}} && \sum_k \sum_j |\mathbf{v}^H \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k \mathbf{w}_j|^2 - 2 \sum_k \text{Re}\{\mathbf{v}^H \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k \mathbf{w}_k\} \\ &\text{subject to} && |v_i|^2 \leq 1, \quad i = 1, \dots, N; \\ & && v_{N+1} = 1; \\ & && \|\mathbf{W}\|_F^2 \leq P; \end{aligned}$$

Equation 4. Problem 1 (P_MSE).

with P the available transmit power at the BS. Note that the constraint $|v_i|^2 \leq 1$ ensures that the i -th RIS element does not amplify the incoming signal, thus guaranteeing a passive structure overall. We remark that contrarily to previous works on beamforming optimization in RIS-aided networks our proposed framework has the key advantage of being convex in the two optimization variables \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{W} separately. *This allows us to find simple and efficient solutions to the problem at hand.* Moreover, thanks to this aforementioned key property the use of alternating optimization between the two optimization variables \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{W} allows us to guarantee convergence to a critical point of **Equation 4**, i.e., a point that satisfies the Karush-Kuhn-Tucker (KKT) conditions of **Equation 4**. Note that given the non-convex nature of **Equation 4**, the KKT conditions are necessary but not sufficient conditions for optimality.

In conclusion, the optimization of RIS-enabled environments will help us provide important contributions to some of the KPIs of Objective 4 in the GA, namely, K5 (reliability) and K6 (increase wireless capacity).

⁶ Note that the last element of \mathbf{v} is introduced to obtain a more compact expression of our optimization problems.

7 In-backhaul learning

Beyond 5G services have very stringent requirements in terms of throughput and latency. DAEMON's architecture addresses the challenge of meeting such demands at different levels of the edge to core continuum. In particular, to achieve a 1-ms response time of the NI algorithms, we bring intelligence at the Transport level, by performing traffic classification directly into the data plane. In this section, we present our study on implementing the inference phase of supervised classification in programmable switches. In Section 7.1 we provide a general introduction and the motivation to perform traffic classification in programmable data plane architectures. In Section 7.2, we describe the Protocol Independent Switch Architecture (PISA) and its hardware limitations. In Section 7.3, we present some examples of inference implemented on PISA architecture.

7.1 Introduction and motivation

With the advent of programmable switches, the possibility to learn from traffic in the data plane at very fast time scale is on the way to become a reality. Such switches are equipped with ASICs (e.g., Intel Tofino) based on the so-called Protocol Independent Switch Architecture (PISA). This flexible architecture allows to design the forwarding logic of the packets via P4 programming language. Few works in literature [65] [66] [67] have investigated the possibility to implement the inference phase of ML models on such pipelines. The most common use case that is mentioned is to perform fast traffic classification in order to respond to delay critical applications or to reply to malicious attacks. To implement ML models on such architectures is not trivial, because of the limited amount of memory and arithmetic operations available in the pipeline. Such constraints represent a barrier for the implementation of complex ML models, as described in section 7.2. As this research field is still in its infancy, no game changing solution has been designed so far. Furthermore, actual implementations very often do not release the code. In this context, our contribution will be to reproduce the most advanced works in literature in order to fully understand their limitations and to find potential room for improvement in terms of classification performance and resource usage.

7.2 PISA architecture

Two are the main stages to process the packets in the pipeline. In the Ingress stage, the headers of incoming packets can be read and manipulated. New headers can be added to the packets. At this stage the forwarding decision is taken. In the Egress stage, once the output port has been selected, it is possible to further elaborate each packet. Figure 45 shows the Ingress pipeline. A programmable parser is responsible of extracting all or just a subset of the packet headers. Relevant fields of the headers are put into a Packet Header Vector (PHV). Such vector then goes through a pipeline of match tables where each content of the PHV can be matched. For each match (or also in case of non-match) an action can be performed. Such actions can apply arithmetic operations, change the data or add new data in the PHV. At the end of the match and action pipeline, a programmable de-parser reassembles the packet putting the data of the PHV into headers. The packet is then logically associated to its final output port and forwarded to a shared-memory buffer. The logic of parser, de-parser and actions and the structure of match tables, can be programmed with P4 language. The P4 code is then compiled and injected into the switch before it starts its operation. The content of the tables and possible parameters needed to perform the actions are sent to the switch as configurations, in order to change its behavior without restarting it.

Figure 45. The Ingress stage of the PISA architecture.

In order to realize the whole pipeline some design restrictions have been made. The total amount of memory that can be used at both Ingress and Egress is 410 Mb. Such memory is partitioned in 32 physical stages where tables and actions can be stored. As the number of resources that are necessary to perform a certain operation is not fixed, physical stages are mapped in one or more logical stages, so that 32 is the maximum number of operations that can be done at both the Ingress or the Egress. Furthermore, the set of instructions that can be applied to packet headers is limited to logical and simple arithmetic

operations (division and floating point operations are not allowed). Finally, the size of the PHV is fixed to 512 B.

The design restrictions of the programmable switch limit the possibility to encode complex ML models into the pipeline. As an example, let us consider the case of N2Net [66]. In this work, the authors implemented the forward pass of an artificial Neural Network (NN) in a PISA architecture. As floating point operations are not allowed, a Binary Neural Network (BNN) model, that uses integer weights, was encoded in the pipeline. The activation vectors of the BNN are stored into the packet headers. Thus, the size of the activations, and consequently the number of neurons of the network, are limited by the dimension of the PHV. The authors mention that with a 32 bits activation vector, a BNN with two layers of 64 and 32 neurons can be run for each packet.

7.3 Methodology

As NN are difficult to encode in the switch pipeline, other works in literature have considered Decision Trees as a better fit for the PISA architecture. In each level of a tree, a simple condition is applied to features the result of which leads to a specific branch of the tree. This kind of structure can be easily encoded in a sequence of match tables where the condition is evaluated by a simple action. Figure 46 shows a possible mapping with one table for each level of the tree.

Figure 46. Logical mapping between match and action elements of the PISA architecture (on the left) and levels of a Decision Tree (on the right).

Following a similar approach, the authors of pForest [67] have implemented Random Forest models pursuing two goals: to achieve a fast classification of flows analyzing just few packets; to optimize the memory usage applying a compression technique on the model features. As we consider this work as the most advanced in literature, we want to reproduce the whole pipeline as a strategy to find potential room for improvement in terms of classification accuracy and memory usage. In pForest, the training phase offline in Python, while the inference is programmed in P4 and executed on a switch with a Tofino ASIC. During the training multiple Random Forest models are generated. These models are context-dependent as they are applied dynamically to flows where at least a minimum number of packets has been collected. Each model must exceed an accuracy threshold to be considered as valid. Once the set of models has been selected, they are encoded into P4 code. The trees of each forest are mapped into tables in a similar fashion depicted in Figure 46. Once the code has been compiled and injected into the switch, the different models can be applied dynamically, according to the specific context, by changing the content of the tables from the controller.

Such results show that it is possible to perform traffic classification with intelligent algorithms directly into the data plane. This is important as it paves the way to the implementation of more memory-efficient and, thus, more performing models to achieve very fast reaction times.

8 Conclusion and outlook

In this document, we discussed the first outcomes of the WP3 work on fast timescale solutions for NI, which have a direct impact at the edge. We discussed how the different NI solutions proposed in this document build towards a fully NI-native ecosystem, and also how they contribute towards the KPIs fulfillment both individually and as a whole. Section 1 introduced the deliverable, describing and categorizing the proposed algorithms and the relationship of D3.1 with requirements identified in WP2. Sections 2 and 3 sat the scene by describing the overall framework and identifying objectives targeted by the developed algorithms in the following sections. In addition, the control loops that represent the templates for DAEMON algorithms are also refined and presented. Section 4 and 5 detailed the proposed algorithms in compute-aware scheduling problem, and multi time-scale problem, respectively. Intelligent reconfigurable surfaces are initially investigated in section 6. Finally, in-network learning solutions undergo a critical review to spot bottlenecks and address them. Overall all four tasks (T3.1, T3.2, T3.3, and T3.4) are tackled and novel contributions relative to the state-of-the-art are identified.

Next, WP3 will focus on the interactions with other WPs, as part of the milestones defined in the project especially towards WP2, with the definition of the architectural aspects introduced in this document, and WP5, for the validation of the algorithms.

9 Appendix A: State of the art

We collect here all the discussion related to the relevant state of the art for the topics addressed by the project.

9.1 Compute aware network functions

There exists a large amount of literature on the management of wireless resources in cellular systems, namely, scheduling and MCS selection mechanisms, with different scenarios and optimization criteria [68], [69], [70]. The advent of virtualized RAN has fostered some research work to understand the relationship between computing and wireless resources, e.g., [71], [72].

The works of [73] and [72] set a theoretical basis for computationally-aware wireless control mechanisms. The former formulates a max-rate optimization problem subject to the availability of computational resources assuming the feasibility of real-valued rate allocation vectors. The later takes a step further and jointly optimizes MCS selection and physical resource block allocation, which results in a more practical approach.

Nonetheless, both works rely on the same model relating computational requirements and SNR, which needs to be pre-calibrated for the platform and scenario they operate, assume full buffers and neglect variations on the arrival bit-rate load, which are certainly well addressed by NI. This issue is addressed in [74], which combines real-time traffic classification and CPU scheduling in a mobile edge computing (MEC) setup although they rely on a very simplistic model.

The work of [71] is one of the first experimental works that study the potential cost savings when exploiting the variations across LTE vRANs' processing load. Nevertheless, the heuristic they propose does not consider variations on the SNR, which we have shown has a great impact on the overall system, and assume that the distribution of the load is known a priori.

The authors of [75] implement PRAN, a programmable LTE vRAN system with dynamic computational resource sharing that however relies on a very simplistic resource demand prediction model. The authors of [76] provide an experimental study on the relationship between throughput and computational demand, but it does not consider contextual dynamics (SNR, traffic load) and also relies on a very simplistic resource demand prediction model.

Regarding the application-aware radio scheduler, several works have been made to identify applications of practical significance. For example, the use case containing both HTTP adaptive streaming and background traffic is targeted in [77] to provide a differentiated treatment with the goal of enhancing customer satisfaction via utility maximization for video quality of all HTTP adaptive streaming and throughput of data flows. Such scheme can be realized by identifying specific port or by deep packet inspection (DPI). Alternative methods of implicit traffic identification also shown quite robust results, but still require expert labeling of the traffic flows [78]. Another work in [79] use the RL on the cross-layer UE state to recognize and differentiate the treatment of a set of key applications (voice, file download, web browsing), without a need for a formal traffic identification step.

9.2 Edge-aware resource orchestration

9.2.1 Edge to cloud orchestration

Due to the plethora of computing resources, the remote cloud centers have been a prominent solution for offering means for hosting and maintaining various Internet-based applications [80]. However, recent technological trends (e.g., Industry 4.0) introduced new challenges that push an urgent need for changing computer and network architectures due to the significant increase in number of connected devices [81]. All these connected devices, such as smartphones, wearables, IoT devices, vehicles, etc., used to send their information to cloud data centers for further processing and decision making [80] [81]. Since cloud resources are usually located at geographically distant computing machines, the increased delay in communication between the device where data originated, and the cloud, impose significant challenge for achieving required levels of Quality of Service (QoS) and Quality of Experience (QoE) [82], [82]. Besides the increase in communication delay, there is also an increase in computation on the cloud (i.e., computational delay), due to the need to process an enormous amount of traffic coming from hundreds and thousands of devices. Thus, the edge computing paradigm has emerged as a promising solution to improve network performance in the 5th generation of wireless networks (5G), while reducing computational delay, transmission delay and bandwidth consumption, via exposing computing resources at the network edge, i.e., closer to the end users/devices where data is produced/consumed [83].

However, opposed to resources in the cloud, edge resources are i) constrained, i.e., the amount of computing resources is limited due to the smaller processors and a limited power budget ii) heterogeneous, as resources might belong to different vendors, and iii) dynamic, i.e., nature of edge resources is fluctuating due to the changes in workload, traffic demand, and users' mobility [83].

Therefore, a proper management of such resources needs to be ensured, in order to use the computing and network resources in an optimized manner.

However, considering strict requirements for 5G networks (e.g., greater coverage, end-to-end latency less than 1ms, massive connectivity, and massive capacity), together with the enormous dynamicity and heterogeneity in edge resources, traditional manual network management becomes impossible to scale and to maintain. Hence, there is a need for transition from a poorly scalable network management to its automation, thereby providing a solution for sophisticated management and orchestration (MANO) that is at the same time compliant to the standards (i.e., ETSI NFV, ETSI MEC, 3GPP) [82]. In the following section, we provide an overview of state-of-the-art MANO solutions that are widely used in both research and industry, with an insight into some recent efforts to apply Artificial Intelligence (AI) to solving edge resource allocation and complex decision-making problems.

9.2.2 MANO solutions

The overall 5G and beyond ecosystems are comprised of the cellular 5G and beyond Systems, as well as a managed and orchestrated infrastructure that provides virtualized network and service functions [15]. The contemporary technologies such as Software Defined Networking (SDN), Network Function Virtualization (NFV), and Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC), are enabling 5G and beyond mobile communication systems to enhance existing use cases and business models, and to foster new ones that were not possible with previous generations [84]. As networks usually comprise a complex set of broad and heterogeneous devices and resources that must be integrated to provide a seamless service, the traditional network management and orchestration solutions that are inherently manual become impossible to maintain [85]. Even more challenging scenarios are present in e.g., automotive industry that has stringent requirements for connected vehicles that move with inherently high speeds. Although the deployment of service instances on top of the distributed cloud resources of cellular network infrastructure edges provides low-latency access to the services from the vehicles, there is a need for fast reconfiguration of the distributed service deployments according to the mobility pattern and associated service and resource demands [15] (e.g., fast scaling, redeployment, migration). Thus, with the heterogeneous and strongly diverse pool of resources and services in 5G and beyond, with complex and potentially conflicting demands, networks need to be flexible, adaptable, and programable, to be able to quickly and smoothly adapt to changes [11]. These requirements need to be supported by technologies, such as virtualization and Artificial Intelligence (AI), in particular Machine Learning (ML), to enable automation and intelligence in the MANO of services, thereby coping with the network complexity.

Edge orchestration can benefit from SDN and NFV because of the opportunity to design a MANO solution as a software-based framework, which can run on a commodity operation system with the procedures of deployment, update, and administration, implemented as a software procedure. One example of such approach is presented by Soenen et al. [86], who built a modular and programmable MANO framework tailored to a service, or a particular VNF. Such service-specific customization is enabled by so-called function-specific managers, and service-specific managers, which are described in VNF Descriptors (VNFDs), and Network Service Descriptors (NSDs).

Some of the open-source orchestration tools that attracted significant attention in past few years are ONAP, OSM, Open Baton, Sonata (5GTango), Tacker, Cloudify, X-MANO, TeNoR, and Escape [87], [88], and the functional analysis of a subset of these MANO solutions is presented in [82], [89], [90]. To compare and study different orchestration solutions, there are different aspects to consider.

- **Support for various virtualization techniques:** As network services nowadays are mostly following the cloud-native principles for deployment due to the opportunities to have a lightweight service suitable for running on the resource-constrained Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) platforms, the support for containerization makes NFV MANO solutions (such as Open Baton, Sonata from 5GTango, latest version of OSM, Tacker, Cloudify, and Escape) candidates for orchestration and management of the latency constrained applications [82].
- **Modularity in software design:** Such modularity for examples enables integration of external monitoring services that provide orchestration layer with the real-time information about the edge services (e.g., supported by ONAP, and Sonata), mitigating the issue of an additional delay in communication between remote external monitoring tools and MANO system.
- **Standard compliance:** ETSI has been the leader in standardizing NFV and MEC, and thus, MANO systems should be designed and developed with reference to the ETSI NFV MANO framework. Such compliance with ETSI standards bridges the gap between different vendors/operators/developers.
- **Multi-domain operation:** The OpenVPN and REST are the technologies that enable communication between edge orchestrators that are in charge of different edge clouds. Thanks to such communication, edge orchestrators can collaborate to optimize their domain-specific operations, via sharing information and resources. One of the examples is X-MANO solution [91] that introduces the federation over multiple domains through the federation agents that are distributed across edge

clouds, federation manager, and OpenVPN as a cross-domain link. Support for multi-domain operations is also provided by ONAP, where multi-site state coordination module enables scaling to multi-site environments to support global scale infrastructure requirements.

However, an agile operation with automated incorporation of changes in service deployments still remains challenging in most of the existing MANO solutions. For addressing such challenge, [92] identifies ML and in general AI as key enablers for increasing automation, where AI-powered mechanisms require fast access to data, abstraction of intelligent and contextual information from events and rule-based systems, supervision, streamlined workflows and lifecycle management. With the support from AI, network optimization can be performed at different timescales, thereby enabling more intelligent MANO operation, which is currently not specified by ETSI NFV MANO. As stated in [92], ETSI ISG NFV considers incorporating AI to the MANO stack, although NFV is not explicitly considering AI in operation automation but rather in requirements to properly feed data and collect actions from AI modules [93]. Currently, the automation mechanisms in NFV-MANO are rule based auto-scaling and auto-healing provided as policies in VNF descriptors. These descriptors provide the description of scale or heal actions to be executed when a condition involving monitoring parameters or VNF indicators is satisfied. The enforcement of auto-scale rule or auto-heal rule occurs in the VNF manager and the NFVO automatically. However, automation procedures are not tackled by ETSI NFV MANO but by standardization groups such as 3GPP SA5, ETSI ISG ZSM, and ETSI ISG ENI.

9.2.3 Resource management techniques for fog/edge computing

Different techniques for handling resource management in cloud and edge computing are given below [94].

Classification of resource management techniques:

- **Discovery:** Discovery is used to find available resources from the cloud, fog, or edge layers, based on workload requirements, to identify where they can be deployed efficiently. It is performed by using a manager or master entity that has an overall view of the resources (e.g., role of orchestrator). Afterwards, based on the workload's requirements, this manager can allocate resources properly among fog and cloud layers. According to Hong and Varghese [80], in the edge/fog computing concept, the discovery algorithms stand for determining resources in the edge network that can be employed for further distributed processing, and based on analysis provided in [80] [94]. some of the mostly utilized edge resource discovery algorithms are Round Robin (RR), Equally Spread Current Execution (ESCE), Shortest Job First (SJF), Gaussian Process Regression for Fog-Cloud Allocation (GPRFCA, Remote Sync Differential Algorithm (RSDA).
- **Load balancing:** Load-balancing distributes the workload to edge nodes to make the operations more efficient by avoiding congestion, low load, and overload. Accordingly, some of the prominent edge load balancing algorithms are Dynamic Resource Allocation Method (DRAM), Efficient Resource Allocation (ERA), Priority based Resource Allocation (PBSA), Feedback-Based Optimized Fuzzy Scheduling Algorithm, Hill Climbing Algorithm, Efficient Load Balancing Algorithm, and Tabu Search Algorithm.
- **Placement:** Placement is used to determine the suitable resources to satisfy the required workload. The main purpose is to distribute the incoming computation tasks to the appropriate fog/edge resources. The iterative algorithm based on resource placement is a method that performs three algorithms: i) it first sorts the edge nodes and application modules according to their environments, ii) it looks for an eligible edge mode that meets module's requirements, and iii) it is responsible for ensuring the requirement check.

As one of the attempts to optimize resource management by applying AI, Fu et al. [83] propose an AI-assisted intelligent wireless network architecture, and based on the proposed architecture, they use deep Q-network (DQN) algorithm to figure out the complex and high-dimensional joint resource allocation problem. Simulation results show that the algorithm has good convergence characteristics, as the proposed architecture and the joint resource allocation scheme achieve better performance compared to other resource allocation schemes. In their approach, the communication, computing and caching resources are virtualized and provided in resource pools, which orchestrator jointly manages and orchestrates by applying AI algorithms. The orchestrator, with the AI algorithm built in, analyzes the system resources status and task attributes to dynamically allocate corresponding computing, caching and communication resources for specific tasks.

9.2.4 Edge computing for video analytic services

An increasing number of wireless services today rely on accurate and fast video analytics. From mobile gaming and augmented reality apps [95] to cognitive assistance [96], autonomous vehicles or surveillance systems [97], user devices capture frames (or, images) from video streams that need to be processed so as to extract critical information, e.g., detect objects of interest. These video analytics are very demanding as they require voluminous data transfers and daunting computations, in almost real time. This renders impractical both their execution at the resource-constrained user devices, and their

transfer to distant cloud servers [98]. A promising solution for adhering to these requirements is, indeed, Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC), where users transmit their video frames for processing to nearby servers equipped with GPUs that implement efficient Neural Networks (NNs).

Indeed, video analytics often employ MEC to improve scalability and latency. For instance, [99] and [100] explore DNN partitioning across user devices, edge servers and the cloud. Other systems like JAGUAR [101], Glimpse [102], OverLay [103] and [104] improve real-time object detection via intelligent encoding, caching, visual space pruning, and on-device tracking, respectively. Additionally, JALAD [105], MobiQoR [106] and DeepDecision [107] explore the accuracy - latency trade off. These important experimental studies reveal the gains of proper configurations, while our experiments further explore the configuration dependence on the system architecture and video data. Optimization-based Approaches.

Configuring these systems, however, requires solving rigorous mathematical problems. DeepDecision [107] formulates a frame-rate/accuracy problem to decide the sampling and DNN model; VideoStorm [108] allocates resources through a utility maximization problem with greedy search of configurations; and [106] minimizes the energy and latency. A convex program is solved in [109] to decide frame sizes, and [110] formulates a similar integer decision problem; while [111] minimizes latency. Another large corpus of works take a computation offloading perspective and handle computing or network resources without considering video analytics (e.g., accuracy) or NN configurations (e.g. NN size); see [112] and survey [113]. Importantly, all above works formulate static model-driven problems, while in practice training data are hardly available and models are valid only for specific systems.

On the other hand, dynamic algorithms can indeed tune better such systems. Chameleon [114] profiles periodically the configurations and searches greedily for the most resource-prudent, but does not consider latency. VideoEdge [115] solves a similar problem for hierarchical systems. An integer program is solved in [116] to allocate computing resources and decide the image compression and DNN model. In [117], video quality and computing resources are selected to maximize successful queries; while [118] uses a Lyapunov algorithm to select frame and NN parameters, and optimizes accuracy under average delay constraints. These interesting works either do not offer optimality bounds [114], [116] or consider asymptotic-only performance [118], assume known models or convex functions. This leaves much space for improvement in this area. Finally, online algorithms for general edge computing, e.g., [119], do not cater for video analytic metrics or the specifics of video pipelines; hence cannot tackle the problem at hand in its entirety.

9.2.5 Radio resource management in wireless networks

As explained before, MEC brings the powerful computation of the cloud near the end-user to, among other goals, fulfill the requirements of delay-sensitive applications like autonomous driving, remote surgery, virtual and augmented reality. However, the resources at the edge are limited and several decision problems must be solved in this new approach.

On one hand, MEC orchestrators now decide which compute-intensive tasks need to be processed by the cloud (computation offloading), by the MEC server or by the end-device, without incurring in performance degradation. Even for some compute-intensive tasks that can be offloaded to the edge or the cloud, it is not possible to upload the input data (e.g., sensor information like videos or images) given some communication bottlenecks. These bottlenecks are caused by the volatile nature of the wireless networks. For instance, wireless links are unreliable as they are i) highly susceptible to interference and ii) wireless links are constantly set up and tear down due to user mobility. Moreover, the uplink and downlink are asymmetric in wireless networks due to the device's lower transmission power. Therefore, in addition to the management of computing resources, the radio resources also must be properly managed to overcome the communication bottlenecks.

9.2.5.1 *State-of-the-art wireless network management*

Due to the explosive growth of wireless connections and massive machine-to-machine communications in the IoT era, spectrum has become a severely scarce resource. Thus, besides the computing resources management challenges presented above, radio resources also require to be optimally scheduled and allocated. Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques are also being proposed in the management of such radio resources, given the ever-increasing size, complexity, and combinatorial nature of wireless networks. Most of the application of AI on wireless networks focus on the mitigation of interference, as one of the most plausible ways to performance degradation.

Interference mitigation can be achieved by controlling the transmission power of end-devices (UE). For instance, Naderializadeh et al. [120], trained two Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) algorithms (A2C and DQN) to decide which UE to serve and what transmission power to use in a scheduling interval. They evaluated their solution in a multi-Base Station setting where each BS is equipped with a learning agent, receives delayed information of their associated users, and communicate with other agents to improve their knowledge about their surroundings. Their distributed Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning (MARL)

framework achieves a performance close to, and even in certain cases outperforming a centralized information-theoretic baseline.

In [121], Calabrese et al. present a RRM architecture consisting of two main building blocks: a learner and an actor. The learner learns RRM policies from data gathered in the network, while the actor executes the RRM policies indicated by the learner. They claim that learner and actor should reside in different network entities; the learner should be a centralized entity (enabling efficient transfer learning for example at the gNB) whose training normally takes hours or days, while the actor(s) should be a decentralized entity whose execution normally takes fractions of a millisecond. Moreover, both entities require entirely different hardware capabilities (GPU vs CPU). This RRM framework was used to solve two specific problems in wireless networks, namely edgeless connectivity, and distributed power control. In edgeless connectivity, users communicate with each other in a device-to-device (D2D) manner by means of joint transmission/reception, coordinated scheduling, and so on. In distributed power control, agents need to jointly adjust their downlink transmission power and user data rate according to the dynamic changes in load distribution and user mobility. The learner is designed to follow a Q-Learning algorithm where, to cope with the large dimensionality of RRM problems they approximate the Q function using a neural network trained with neural-fitted Q-iteration and ensemble learning.

Another way to cope with interference is to carefully select communication parameters that enable co-located transmissions to take place. For instance, the operation of long-term evolution (LTE) in unlicensed spectrum (LTE-U) has been proposed to cope with the ever-increasing mobile traffic demand. However, the deployment of LTE in such bands implies sharing spectrum with mature technologies such as IEEE 802.11 (Wi-Fi). In this regard, Maglogiannis et al. [122] propose an adaptive LTE-U algorithm (mLTE-U) that uses a variable transmission opportunity (TXOP), followed by a variable muting period. This muting period can be exploited by co-located networks to gain access to the medium. Then, they enhanced mLTE-U with a Q-learning algorithm to autonomously select the appropriate TXOP and muting periods that can provide fair coexistence between co-located mLTE-U and other networks. They showed that the Q-Learning algorithm can identify the best configuration of TXOP and muting periods in the specific case where mLTE-U is coexisting with Wi-Fi networks, outperforming conventional selection schemes.

Due to the highly heterogeneous wireless ecosystem, it is uncertain whether only one technology will be able to fulfil the multiplicity of service requirements. In that sense, non-3GPP technologies, and more specifically, Wi-Fi, also must undergo a radical architectural shift to cope with the dynamism, higher-speed, and almost unlimited capacity required by next-generation services. In that sense, Channel Bonding (CB) is one of the most recent standard-compliant technique to enhance spectral utilization. Under CB, channels ranging from 40MHz (802.11n) up to 320MHz (802.11be) can be formed by bonding several primary channels. More recently, this bonding can be dynamically done in a per-frame basis at the moment of transmission, according to the current spectrum occupation. Given the uncoordinated nature of Wi-Fi networks, the performance of Dynamic Channel Bonding (DCB) is highly compromised in dense deployments, leading to known problems such as hidden and exposed nodes. Therefore, intelligent spectrum access strategies are of the utmost importance to accomplish QoS requirements of all connected devices.

In this regard, Soto et al. [45], propose a data-driven approach based on Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) that exploits the information carried in the deployment's topology to predict the performance of Wi-Fi networks. With this prediction, controllers in an SDN-like wireless network can assess how positively or negatively a given decision will impact the performance of the network. For instance, from collected metrics, controllers can have a view on the current state of the network, if the performance is decaying due to a given channel allocation, then the controller can easily evaluate the expected performance of a different configuration thanks to the learned network model (GNN). Once the expected performance given by the GNN is better than the actual performance, then the configuration that maximizes the expected performance can be applied to the network.

Similar to the wired ecosystem, wireless networks also required to be properly managed to cope with the stringent requirements in next-generation services. Through the Network Monitoring Service (NMS) the traffic of a network domain can be analyzed to determine which applications affect network the most in terms of total bandwidth usage or identify the most critical links so decision-making engines for network management can ensure fast troubleshooting and securing high QoS to the users. More recently, the NMS has been enhanced with Machine Learning (ML) techniques to perform automatic network traffic analysis such as network state predictions, anomaly detection, malware detection, and Traffic classification (TC). TC allows inferring the application that is generating the traffic flowing through the network. In this way, security and QoS policies can be enforced on each flow. In general, the TC task has been done using port numbers or inspecting the application payload. Using port numbers is nowadays unreliable due to dynamic port negotiation. Examining the application payload assumes that the inspected traffic belongs to the same network domain and over a byte/protocol representation of the packet at the Link Layer L2 (or above). These assumptions limit the capabilities of TC systems in wireless networks using a shared spectrum. Users' traffic transmissions can negatively impact the users' traffic from one wireless network domain without being noticed by the TC system. The transmissions from other

wireless devices may not be demodulated, decoded, or delivered to the upper radio stack layers because either 1) the devices' wireless technologies are different, or 2) they are the same but belong to a different network domain (and its traffic can be encrypted). Flow-based approaches [123] have also been used for TC, but they are limited in the sense that they require to capture the beginning of the flow. More recently, Deep Learning (DL) approaches have been used [124], [125] to overcome the limitations of the approaches mentioned above. They report great accuracy and can work with encrypted and wireless traffic.

9.2.6 Challenges in edge orchestration

With the introduction of Edge Computing paradigms, two new variants for learning at the edge are born, i) to use ML to optimize the communication at the edge (ML for communication (MLC)) or ii) to use the communication network to enable advanced techniques of ML (Communications for ML (CML)). Both variants can form a loop, the more optimal the communication is, the better and more accurate ML models can be developed to improve the performance of the communication network.

This opens also new challenges and paradigms of distributed, low latency and reliable ML at the edge [126], [127]. Some of the challenges are summarized as follows.

- **Large amount of unevenly generated data.** In fog/edge computing, each device can be considered as a small compute server [80]. However, the inter-device coordination of these nodes is an orchestration task, which is challenging compared to the cloud environment as all nodes belong to NFV infrastructure (NFVI) that can be used for hosting a various set of services. This imposes significant burden for the orchestrators as they need to monitor and consider i) a large amount of data from a number of edge devices that is greater than a number of compute servers in a cloud data center, while performing MANO operations. This might be additionally constrained by edge devices that are mobile, as their connectivity to the network may not be stable, which leads to the delays in data collection. Moreover, the generated data is not evenly distributed among the different nodes. That means that, while one part of the network might have access to a huge amount of data, other part of the network will have difficulties to access to a tiny fraction of the data. This hinders the applicability of data-driven approaches where the general rule of thumb is to have more data to increase their accuracy or performance. Therefore, one of the open challenges is how do we learn from few data?
- **Federation aspects.** Edge compute nodes may consist of thousands to millions of moving devices such as cars and drones, whose management needs to be coordinated by orchestrators. Due to the distributed scope, it is challenging to orchestrate the management of the devices using existing cloud management platforms such as OpenStack, FocusStack, Foggy, and Kubernetes, and some additional orchestration layer is needed to ensure the cooperation and federation between different devices/groups of NFVI resources.
- **Edge suitability for running AI.** Due to the resource constraints, edge nodes are not suitable for running heavyweight data processing tools such as Apache Spark and deep learning libraries. An alternative lightweight data processing tool such as Apache Quarks can be employed in resource-limited edge devices, but it lacks advanced data analytics functions. The imbalance between lightweight implementations and high performance needs to be addressed. Moreover, wireless links are constantly set up and tear down due to the UE's mobility. Therefore, permanent access to data or predictions cannot be ensured under an unreliable infrastructure. In such cases, the training and the communication must be jointly optimized to ensure convergence.
- **Reducing latency in real-time constrained tasks.** For the purpose of reducing latency in the time-constrained workloads, accelerator scheduling algorithms that consider real-time characteristics are required in edge nodes. Although highly utilized in edge computing environments, efficient accelerator management in containers has not been sufficiently explored. Federated Learning (FL) [128] is an emerging ML architecture that can cope with the previously mentioned challenges. In FL, edge devices periodically exchange the parameters (e.g., weights and gradients) during local training to build a global view of the network state. This operation mode ensures data privacy and improve communication efficiency.
- **Workload partitioning between edge and cloud.** Hierarchical edge computing exploits both conventional cloud computing and recent fog/edge computing. In general, tasks that need prompt reaction are processed in fog/edge devices whereas long-term analysis tasks are performed at the cloud. However, it is challenging how to partition a single large workload into small tasks and distribute them to both the cloud and fog/edge for concurrent executions. An efficient partitioning method and task placement strategy based on accurate prediction are required.
- **Realistic experimentation.** As most of the research in edge resource management and orchestration is based on the simulation results, using simulation tools such as iFogSim, EdgeCloudSim, CloudAnalyst, SimCloud, Cloudlet tool, OMNET++, with only a few infrastructure

options available for pursuing real fog/edge computing environments, there is a need for realistic and large-scale fog/edge testbeds [94]. Moreover, typical ML workflows consider two operational modes, namely, training and inference. During training, the ML model is allowed to make mistakes (e.g., take random actions, misclassification errors) which leads to a poorly behavior and possibly to faulty communications. Nonetheless, errors in the communications are costly and must be avoided. In this regard, [39, p.] considers ML pipelines connected to emulation/simulation sandboxes where they can safely train with (close-to) real data and preliminary model testing [129]. After meeting a performance target, already trained models can be safely deployed to perform inference (e.g., predict) in production networks.

- **Model generalization.** Due to the dynamic changes in the network environment, neural networks models need to be adjusted and retrained. In [83], authors introduce the concept of transfer learning as a way to better cope with dynamic network environments and neural network retraining, as transfer learning can model the target domain better using the knowledge from the source domain, when data distribution, feature dimension and model output change dynamically.
- **Training problems for large scale networks with limited computing capabilities.** As large-scale wireless networks produce a large amount of data that needs to be processed by ML models, and these models also need to be trained with a large amount of data, it will require a lot of time and high computation capabilities for a single server. Distributed machine learning recognized as a potential solution as it provides data parallelism where different server nodes are running the same ML model, but with different type of data.

9.3 Reconfigurable intelligent surfaces

While the theoretical modelling of RIS-aided wireless networks is well studied, many challenges are still open to be tackled such as building testbeds for experimental validation [130], the task of estimating the combined channel from the BS to the RIS and on to the UE [131] and the joint optimization of the multi-antenna BS and the RIS parameters [132], [133], [134], [135], [136], [64]. In [132] the authors analyze a single-UE case and propose to maximize the rate. The resulting non-convex optimization problem is solved via both fixed point iteration and manifold optimization. A similar setting is analyzed in [131], where the authors propose a heuristic solution to the non-convex maximization of the received signal power with similar performance to conventional semidefinite relaxation (SDR). The single-UE setting is also studied in [136], where the authors propose to encode information both in the transmitted signal and in the RIS configuration. A multiuser setting is analyzed in [133] where the authors propose to maximize the minimum receive SNR among all UEs in the large system regime. While this approach guarantees fairness among UEs, it might not maximize the system sum rate. In [134], the authors design jointly the beamforming at the BS side and the RIS parameters by minimizing the total transmit power at the BS, given a minimum receive signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) requirement. This framework was later extended to consider low resolution RISs in a single UE setting [135]. Finally, in [64], the authors proposed a joint optimization of mmWave-aided precoder parameters and RISs passive beamforming parameters, considering quantized phase shifters, common in practical settings.

9.4 Energy aware operation

9.4.1 Energy-aware code offloading

The energy consumption of edge-based infrastructures is jointly determined by the use of CPU, storage, memory and network interfaces. Since the contribution of the CPU is dominant among these factors, it is the main focus of attention in the literature [58]. There are two models that are mainly used to determine power consumption: the first is based on the DVFS (Dynamic Voltage and Frequency Scaling) [137] technique, which considers the frequency at which the processor is working at a given time to determine the energy consumption; and the other approach is based on the observation that infrastructures power consumption is linear to the CPU utilization ratio [138], which depends on the computational load.

Software power consumption is not only attributable to applications themselves or any executing code, but also depends on the device hardware characteristics on which the coding is running. In multi-device infrastructures, it is possible to reduce the energy consumption of applications by offloading some computation intensive tasks onto nearby edge devices so that it can be possible to reduce the system overall energy consumption.

An optimal assignment of tasks to devices and cloud enables edge-based infrastructures to reduce the power consumption not only of the user's device, but also of the entire infrastructure (or of the selected devices), while maintaining a certain QoS. In fact, it is possible to provide a quasi-optimal task assignment making a trade-off between energy and latency. The aforementioned phenomenon is one of the principles behind code offloading proposals, where parts of the software pieces are delegated to other devices from the user's one or the cloud.

Then, offloading algorithms are of central importance for efficient coordination among the nodes involved. Commonly most of them consider several factors including device energy, bandwidth utilization cost, network connectivity, workload, and application latency. While most code offloading proposals that aim to minimize power consumption only focus on the user's device, others focus on the entire infrastructure or even allow configuring the devices where power needs to be minimized [59].

Existing code offloading approaches differ with respect to the type of edge nodes considered for offloading and the number of users considered. More differences can be found among offloading approaches [139] in the objectives that drive code offloading (e.g., reduce power consumption, latency, etc.); the nodes considered (user node, all nodes, edge and cloud etc.); the partition and the granularity level, the task model used, and the mechanisms employed to obtain the solution. The granularity level refers to the size of the computational load or components that can run remotely.

The partition granularity, which is determined by each approach, has a significant impact in the offloading and in the improvement achieved. Mostly, three different levels of granularity are found: method, task or, services or functions (from the smallest scale to the biggest). The more fine-grained the granularity, the more flexible and complex the offloading solution is. The most popular is the task module level. The offloading partition determines which parts of the user application are offloaded and the order of execution. The task model determines the use of the offloading partition scheme, mainly binary (i.e. static) or partial (i.e. dynamic) offloading [140]; in the binary offloading tasks cannot be further partitioned (also known as static partition). Most of the binary offloading approaches use a graph to model tasks flow relationships, tasks' costs (CPU, memory) and dependencies in terms of provided/produced and required/consumed data. Partial (or dynamic partition) offloading allows splitting tasks into simpler components, being resource allocation the key problem of this kind of scheme.

Most approaches that address the problem of task allocation in code offloading use heuristic algorithms or solve this problem using integer linear programming (ILP), mixed integer linear/nonlinear programming (MILP/MINLP), and SMT (satisfiability modulation theories) solvers. The static/binary task offloading is usually a typical MILP/MINLP problem and is generally an NP-hard problem. A concurrent challenge mainly discussed in the last decade's literature is that some situations are considered colossal due to the number of parameters involved at the same time, and the impossibility to specifically rank the power consumption of them all. Hence, the commented approaches are tuned with machine learning approaches to include quality predictions in task-offloading like analyses [141]. Another concurrent issue that increases the complexity of the analyses is the power consumption that can arise between sets of components, where the literature states that levels of interactions larger than 5 are NP-Complete problems, but also concludes that a maximum level of 3 is sufficient [142]. In any case, to improve the scalability of the interactions analyses, probability and statistical approaches are suggested [143]. Finally, to double-check that the results obtain by making use of probability and prediction are truly meaningful, normality tests are applied to the results [144].

On the other hand, when the configuration space is extremely large and compromises the ranking of the energy consumption, recent studies propose to narrow the search range by adapting the software resource requirements to the available Edge resources [145]. Nevertheless, in other cases the available resources in the current infrastructure are not enough to provide a certain QoS, being the Edge resources that must adapt to the software requirements.

Applying these concepts to DAEMON, we propose to use the advantages of edge computing and code offloading proposals to perform an optimal allocation of VNFs among the infrastructure devices, with the objective of minimizing energy consumption and making a trade-off with other system qualities. In the DAEMON project, we need to predict the power consumption of executing a VNF in any device, considering they can be heterogeneous. In addition, we should explore the possibility of selecting certain nodes (e.g., cloud, edge or user nodes) where the optimization deployment algorithm should focus on. In these cases, it would be preferable to consider the energy saving on certain nodes, and not the overall system (if necessary). Other indicators, such as the carbon footprint of the power that feeds each node, could also be considered. Finally, the energy saving of the optimal placement of VNFs, CNFs and PNFs should overrule the energy cost.

10 References

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